

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D4.1 Trial planning and experimentation methodology

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3 rd generation Partnership Project
5G PPP	5G Public Private Partnership
6G-IA	6G Industry Association
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CDF	Common Data Format
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CQI	Channel Quality Indicator
CSV	Comma Separated Value
DL	Downlink
DT	Digital Twin
DNN	Data Network Name
E2E	End to End
ETSI	EU Telecommunications Standards Institute
ExpB	Experiment Blueprint
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GUI	Graphic User Interface
HW	Hardware
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identifier
IP	Internet Protocol
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LCM	Life Cycle Manager
LoS	Line of Sight
MANO	Management and Orchestration

Abbreviation / Term	Description
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MRT	Measurement Report Template
NA	Not Applicable
NetApps	Network Applications
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NSA	Non-Stand Alone
NSSAI	Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
OSM	Open-Source MANO (Management & Orchestration)
PDR	Packet Delivery Ratio
QoS	Quality of Service
R&I	Research and Innovation
RAN	Radio Access Network
RTT	Round Trip Time
Rx	Receiver
SA	Stand Alone
SW	Software
TC	Testcase
TCB	Testcase Blueprint
Tx	Transmitter
UC	Use Case
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
UPF	User Plane Function

VA	Vertical Agnostic
VM	Virtual machine
VNF	Virtual Network Function

VS	Vertical Specific
VSID	Vertical Service ID
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable constitutes the first deliverable of WP4 of VITAL-5G, providing key information about the trialling and experimentation processes, the initial trial planning per testbed, the common format to report and store data, the tools to be used for data collection and processing, as well as the complete list of Testcases as defined by each of the three VITAL-5G experimentation facilities and the trialling guidelines and user manual.

WP4 has been active since M9 of the project, focusing on the design of straightforward and effective processes to facilitate the trial execution and results collection. The designed trialling and experimentation methodology provides a clear overview of all the steps that an experimenter (internal and external) using the VITAL-5G platform and facilities must take, to ensure proper configuration of the experiment, proper reporting, logging and storing of the necessary data, as well as the interfaces and tools involved in processing and evaluating the outcome of the trials.

A measurement framework has been designed by the project encompassing commonly reported KPIs by all testbeds/facilities, to assist with the global evaluation of the NetApps performance and to provide insights regarding the 5G connectivity performance and added value for the T&L sector as a whole. Besides the common reporting, which is based on a Common Data Format (CDF) and automatic and manual reporting using the same tools, custom KPIs have also been defined by each of the VITAL-5G facilities to allow for the evaluation of the specificities of the three targeted T&L Use Cases, each containing multiple services. The combination of the common and custom KPIs will allow for a thorough end-to-end evaluation of the 5G testbeds, the T&L services and the NetApps.

As part of their preparation for the trial phase, each of the VITAL-5G facilities have defined an initial planning of experimentation activities spanning until the end of the project. These time-plans reflect the current best estimates of the VITAL-5G partners involved in each facility with regards to the upcoming cycles of trialling → results collection & processing → performance evaluation → updates based on insights gained → re-trialling, and they include the 3rd party experimentation phases (allowing time for 3rd party experimenters to use the VITAL-5G facilities). Moreover, in an effort to be as efficient as possible and to carefully design each aspect of the trials, all three VITAL-5G facilities have defined extensive lists of Testcases, based on the agreed common template of D1.4 [3], describing in detail all the aspects of each of the tests to be performed in each of the testbeds. These testcases cover both service-oriented experiments and network-oriented experiments. Examples from each facility are provided in the Annex, while the entirety of the testcases can be found on the project's common workspace, Teamwork.

Finally, a handy experimentation/user manual has been included in this deliverable, to assist both internal and external experimenters, providing key information about the experimentation process in VITAL-5G, including preparatory lists, configuration steps, trial execution steps and results collection and processing guidelines.

1 Introduction

This document comprises the first deliverable of WP4, originating from Task 4.1 Planning and setup of the trials. As such, it addresses several of WP4's objectives including:

- *Definition of trial preparation methodology and trial execution guidelines*: This is the main objective of this deliverable. To support the proper operation of such complex trialling environments as the VITAL-5G trial facilities/sites and to coordinate and align their activities, requires the creation of clear guidelines and experimentation methodologies supported by the necessary common formats and tools to enable experimentation under common rules. The common experimentation methodology and tools presented in this deliverable, will enable the synchronised trialling and evaluation processes across the three VITAL-5G trial sites and among 3rd party experimenters, allowing for global insights regarding the added-value of 5G communications and NetApps for the Transport & Logistic (T&L) sector which are greater than the individual conclusions offered by each trial site.
- *To perform trial coordination, interworking and progress monitoring*: Common experimentation stages have been defined by VITAL-5G to allow for experimentation planning and reporting using common terms. These experimentation stages cover both internal and external (3rd party) experimentation and allow for the creation of trial planning schedules, which can be continuously monitored and updated according to real-life circumstances. As such, the coordination and alignment among the different sites and potential interworking among them becomes more straightforward.
- *To support consortium internal and external 3rd party experimenters for setting-up of their trials*: In order to support both internal and external experimentation over the VITAL-5G platform and respective facilities, clear guidelines and instructions have been created acting as a “user manual”, where the step-by-step process that any experimenter should follow is described. Moreover, common formatting, methodologies and tools have been created to facilitate the aligned results collection and processing, as well as their cross-comparison to assist with the drawing of communal insights and conclusions.
- *To perform comprehensive technical KPI analysis and validation*: In order to enable a comprehensive technical KPI analysis and validation, clear KPI collection methodologies and tools are needed, which are defined in this document. Moreover, the commonly agreed KPI format among the VITAL-5G partners and the automated process to collect and report these metrics from all three experimentation sites will enable the proper evaluation of the respective NetApps and testbeds and the thorough validation of all use cases, while it will also allow for global insights across all three facilities.

The added-value of this deliverable lies in the fact that it will act both as an internal synchronization document that will assist project partners to align their work and use common methodologies for experimentation and results collection and analysis, as well as a useful user manual for 3rd party experimenters wishing to use the VITAL-5G platform and the experimentation facilities. The facility trial planning schedule comprises the current best estimate of the three facilities and will be constantly updated to reflect real-time changes (e.g., due to delays in HW delivery, or malfunctions), thus assisting in the coordination and oversight of the three facilities.

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed. Table 1 provides this matching for deliverable D4.1.

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
WP4, Task 4.1 Description	The general guidelines and trial preparation methodology to be followed by all VITAL-5G trials will be defined in this task to ensure a comprehensive and detailed trial approach and the delivery of homogeneous and detailed results to Tasks 4.4 and WP5 for the purpose of KPI validation	Section 2	The overall trialling methodology to be followed by all experimenters using the VITAL-5G platform (both internal and 3 rd parties) is described in Section 2 of this deliverable, including the overview of the experimentation process and cycles, the trialling tools at the disposal of the experimenters, the metrics collection and storage methodology, the results analysis methodology (after collection) and the necessary consent forms that all experimenters must sign. This will provide the broad picture of the steps that an experimenter needs to take, while the specificities of each of the above steps are provided in the following sections.
WP4, Task 4.1 Description	The trialling methodology will at least include a) stepwise approach for the completion of a test run from set-up to configuration, to calibration, to testing and finally to trial and results collection per trial site	Section 2, Section 5	Besides the overview of the experimentation process which is provided in Section 2, a targeted User/Trialling manual has been created and presented in Section 5 to facilitate all VITAL-5G experimenters. This manual includes the trial preparation checklist, the steps necessary to set-up and configure an experiment, the steps necessary for trial execution and the steps necessary for the results collection and storage.
WP4, Task 4.1 Description	b) a time-plan per trial site for the testing, trialling and validation periods (cycles) expected by internal and 3 rd party experimenters	Section 4	The VITAL-5G project has defined 8 different stages of the experimentation process, to facilitate the trial planning and the alignment of schedules among the trial sites. A detailed trial plan per trial site, based on the defined stages, is provided in Section 4, including provisions for 3 rd party experimentation.

WP4, Task 4.1 Description	c) the tools to be used per trial for (meta)data and KPI collection, the aligned storage data formatting and respective data storing facilities	Section 3	In order to ensure the correct collection of metrics during trials, that will lead to the necessary evaluation goals, common methodologies and tools have been designed to guarantee that all necessary metrics will be collected. Section 3 presents the common experimentation / measurement framework that the VITAL-5G partners have agreed upon and the data models and tools that will enable the proper collection of KPIs during trials and will allow for cross-comparability and communal insights.
WP4, Task 4.1 Description	d) experimenter interaction guidelines with the VITAL-5G platform and the open repository for the creation and setup of an experiment.	Section 5	As one of the main goals of VITAL-5G is to attract external (3 rd party) experimenters, it was deemed necessary to create an “experimenter’s manual” containing instructions and guidelines that will facilitate the onboarding of 3 rd party experimenters and will act as an easy -one-stop-document/reminder for internal experimenters. Section 5 presents all the necessary information on how to prepare, set-up, configure, run and collect the results from an experiment.
DELIVERABLE			
<p><u>D4.1 Trial planning and experimentation methodology</u></p> <p>This deliverable will provide details on the trial planning of each facility, the used tools and the experimentation methodology to be followed by the VITAL-5G facilities users, as well as early results from the internal experimentation of T4.2.</p>			

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable comprises the continuation of necessary deliverables to allow for the understanding and use of the VITAL-5G platform and experimentation facilities. The targeted Use Cases (UC) have been described in [1], while the components of the VITAL-5G platform and its key functionalities have been described in [2]. The architecture of the targeted NetApps and other key components has been described in [4], while the overview of the vertical facilities and the detailed architecture of the utilized testbeds by each facility has been described in [6]. This deliverable practically describes how to make use of all the above facilities, components and systems in order to perform experiments over the VITAL-5G platform and to ensure the proper collection, storage and processing of the trial results. The remainder of this report is structured as follows:

- Section 2 provides the overview of the VITAL-5G trialling methodology and tools
- Section 3 presents the VITAL-5G measurement framework including the commonly agreed KPI format, the common KPIs to be measured/reported and the agreed reporting template
- Section 4 Provides the targeted trial planning of the three experimentation facilities and the Testcases that each of them will apply during trials
- Section 5 provides the user/trialling manual for experimenters
- Section 6 concludes the document

2 VITAL-5G Trialling Methodology

This section describes the end-to-end trialling methodology that will be used during the VITAL-5G trials at the three VITAL-5G facilities (Antwerp, Athens and Galati) by both internal and external (3rd party) experimenters. This includes the experimentation methodology and processes defined to ensure the proper experiment execution, the format in which the various metrics will be recorded and stored, the agreed KPIs to be recorded in each site facility, the tools used to collect, report and store the respective measurements as well as the general guidelines for the results analysis methodology to be followed after the trials have been executed.

2.1 Experimentation methodology & processes

The goal of the experimentation methodology designed within VITAL-5G is to provide clear processes and the respective tools, to ensure that all experiments executed over the VITAL-5G facilities, have been set-up and configured properly prior to the experiment execution, that all necessary metrics are being recorded/logged using a common format that will facilitate their post-processing and cross-comparison, that all sites offer all the necessary information to allow for the proper evaluation of the NetApp functionality and the respective UCs and that experimenters have clear guidelines as to how to prepare and execute an experiment over the VITAL-5G premises, where and how the trial metrics are being stored and processed, which experimental reports need to be filled in and how the post-experimental evaluation takes place. Figure 1 below, depicts the end-to-end VITAL-5G experimentation methodology on a high level.

Figure 1: VITAL-5G end-to-end experimentation methodology

The experimentation procedure described in Figure 1 entails the different processes and tools that an experimenter will follow or needs to be aware of and will be described in detailed in the following sections of this deliverable. The parts comprising the end-to-end VITAL-5G experimentation methodology are:

- **User/Trialling Manual:** In order to assist both internal and external (3rd party) experimenters a user manual has been created, containing instructions on how to execute an experiment over the VITAL-5G platform and which processes are involved. These are useful guidelines for all experimenters and highlight the preparation steps that need to be taken prior to the execution of an experiment,

instructions on how to set-up and configure an experiment over the VITAL-5G platform and the selected site facility and how the results are collected and analysed. The user manual is provided in Section 5.

- **Trial preparation checklist**: This is a list containing the necessary steps that an experimenter needs to take before initiating an experiment over the VITAL-5G platform. It is part of the overall guidelines offered by the user manual, but due to its importance it can also be considered as a quick reference guide to set-up and experiment. The checklist is presented in detail in Section 5.1.
- **Trial/Experiment set-up**: The experimenters need to set-up and configure their experiment via the **Service, Testing & Experiment Manager** which resides in the VITAL-5G portal. Via this module the experimenters will select the desired settings and variable values that will define each experiment. In order to fully organize and keep track of this process, and to ensure the replicability of all experiments under the exact same conditions the VITAL-5G has defined a **Testcase (TC)** template as part of its testing and validation methodology defined in deliverable D1.4 [3]. Using this template, each VITAL-5G site facility has defined its own network oriented and service oriented testcases, in order to measure and evaluate the performance of the testbed and the performance of the NetApps and targeted UCs, respectively. The defined TCs (which define the experiments that will be executed in each of the VITAL-5G sites) per site facility are described in Section 4.2. External (3rd party) experimenters will also have to create their own TCs, based on the defined template, in order to execute an experiment over the VITAL-5G platform.
- **Trial/Experiment execution**: As soon as the experiment has been defined and configured the experiment execution phase begins, which invokes the measurement framework process, in order to log and transmit all the necessary metrics during experiment execution.
- **Measurement Framework**: The measurement framework defines which metrics/KPIs are being logged/recorded during each experiment, how these values are measured, where are they stored and under which format. The goal is to ensure uniformity in experimentation data logging which will allow for a more straightforward post-processing and will facilitate cross-comparison of data and the extraction of global insights. The VITAL-5G measurement framework is presented in detail in Section 3 and it is comprised of three main parts:
 - **Common KPIs / Automatic reporting**: As all experiments have some commonalities (performed over a 5G testbed, using VNF and NetApps, etc.) some common KPIs have been defined by VITAL-5G (as presented in Section 3.1) which will be automatically logged during experiment execution and reported by each site facility via the **Service & Network Monitoring** module of the platform. The same metrics will also be reported to the **Results Analytics & Diagnostics** module of the platform to enable the diagnosis of performance bottlenecks. These KPIs will be used to draw global conclusions regarding the performance of the various testbeds and NetApps based on the selected variables.
 - **Custom KPIs / Manual reporting**: Besides the commonly reported KPIs, custom KPIs will also be logged and reported per experiment, as the different experiments address different UCs and use different NetApps. The exact KPIs to be logged and reported per experiment are described in the respective section of each Testcase, thus making it clear what will be the output of each experiment. As these KPIs differ per site, it made no sense to define a common list, however a common format of reporting them has been defined as described in Section 3.1.2
 - **Measurement Reporting template**: In order to facilitate the full reporting of experimental metrics (both common and custom KPIs) and their respective evaluation, a common Measurement Reporting Template (MRT) has been defined which all project partners and external experimenters will use, to report the findings of each experiment. The MRT is described in more detail in Section 3.3.
- **Results storage & Analysis**: Besides the data collected during the experiment execution and automatically reported via the monitoring framework, all relevant experimental data (manual CSV files, MRTs) will be stored at the ORO provided facilities hosting the VITAL-5G platform and will be accessible for post-processing. The analysis of the data and the performance evaluation of the respective NetApps

and UCs will take place in Task 4.4 and the outcomes will be reported in the follow up deliverables D4.2 and D4.3. The processes that have been defined to help guide the analysis and evaluation procedures are described in Section 2.3, while the results collection and storage processes are described in Section 5.4.

The experimentation methodology described in this section provides a high-level view of the tools and processes comprising the experimentation cycles of VITAL-5G, and is meant to assist both internal and external experimenters to better structure their reporting and facilitate the respective evaluation processes.

2.2 Experimentation / Trialling tools

The VITAL-5G platform provides a number of tools to facilitate the execution of experiments, the collection of metrics and KPIs and their analysis to identify potential issues or bottlenecks in the end-to-end deployment, in particular NetApps or in specific segments of network connectivity that impact the overall service performance. All experimentation tools can be accessed by the experimenters through the **web GUI of the VITAL-5G Portal**, which offers a single access point during the various experimentation phases, as follows:

- In the experiment design phase, the experimenter can browse the **Test Case Blueprints (TCBs) and Experiment Blueprints (ExpB)** available in the **VITAL-5G catalogue** and/or onboard new blueprints. TCBs and ExpBs (inherited from the 5G EVE project¹) provide a common template to describe the tests to be performed (e.g., the scripts to be launched during the execution of an experiment, their configuration parameters, the metrics and KPIs to be collected from the network and computing infrastructure or from the NetApps, the criteria to aggregate, process and evaluate them, etc.) and they can be customized to differentiate the various testing campaigns.
- The experimenters can schedule, launch, monitor and terminate experiments associated to a running vertical service directly from the VITAL-5G Portal, with the possibility to select different test cases and configure them. The **Experiment Lifecycle Manager (LCM)** in the VITAL-5G platform will coordinate the experiment execution activating the platform components responsible for the result analysis and diagnostic and, if needed, to trigger the configuration and execution of scripts for testing automation. Support for manual actions during the experiment execution and manual experiment termination is also provided, to efficiently deal with trials that require human interactions.
- During the execution of the experiment, infrastructure and service metrics are automatically collected from the various testbeds and service NetApps in the **centralized Monitoring Platform**, using common interfaces and a common data format (CDF). In particular, the various metrics are encoded in JSON messages which are published on a ZeroMQ bus using well-defined topics to facilitate their filtering and consumption (see section 3.1 for further details). Once collected, these raw metrics can be further elaborated with configurable rules through the **Result Analytics** component, which produces custom, experiment-specific KPIs based on formulas which can be specified by the experimenters. The resulting KPIs are also published on the ZeroMQ bus, to make them available in the Monitoring Platform.
- From the web GUI of the VITAL-5G Portal, the experimenter can visualize metrics and KPIs through configurable **monitoring dashboards**. Moreover, real-time and historical monitoring data can be consumed and retrieved using programmable APIs, enabling further processing on external or third-party systems at the experiment runtime or after its termination. The size of the storage for keeping historical data and the duration of the data persistency can be configured as needed on a per-service basis.
- After the experiment termination, the metrics originally collected by the Monitoring Platform and the KPIs generated by the Result Analytics are post-processed by the **Diagnostic** component, which provides additional insights about the service performance or the causes of potential performance degradation.

¹ <https://www.5g-eve.eu/>

For each experiment execution, a report is automatically generated with a summary of the most relevant results and it can be visualized through the VITAL-5G Portal.

Beyond these tools for automated testing and results analysis, VITAL-5G has defined procedures and common templates to manually collect, aggregate, elaborate and consolidate trial results, possibly combining measurements from multiple experiments. Further details about the measurement reporting template are provided in section 3.3.

2.3 Results analysis methodology

2.3.1 General considerations

The results collected from the various test devices will be analyzed with either *quantitative* or *qualitative* data analysis depending on the outputs. The results of the use cases will be analyzed as data compared with the KPIs criteria, from which the performance will be computed and then the T&L-specific 5G network will be diagnosed if there are any errors. Another purpose of the KPI-based analysis is to verify if the network offers the required performance parameters. The service-level KPIs are important because if these KPIs are met the correct functioning of the VITAL-5G network can be achieved and demonstrated to possible clients of the 5G technology developed. Thus, all integrated sensors will be tested by observing their correct functioning and monitoring the application's outputs so that it redirects to the correct NetApps using the API endpoints.

Some of the most important results of the VITAL-5G project can be achieved by analyzing the properties of the 5G network. The methodology used in analyzing the defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) is based on the data and information that comes from the VITAL-5G environment.

2.3.2 Data preparation

The numerical data should be verified if it contains errors because these errors can affect the analysis of the results. The data that comes from the sensors can be:

- incomplete data: if some of the values that characterize the data are missing or some attributes that characterize the data are missing or we only have aggregate work data.
- noisy data, which means that the data contains errors or extraordinary values.
- inconsistent data, which means that there are discrepancies in codes or names.

The process of data preparation is based on the following operations:

- *selection of relevant data*: selection of attributes (filtering and packaging methods), elimination of anomalies or elimination of duplicate records.
- *data reduction*: sampling or selection of courts.

Data preparation generates quality data, which leads to quality patterns. It will be possible to:

- recover incomplete data, which means that we will no longer have missing values, or that ambiguity will be reduced.
- purify the data, which consists of a process of correcting errors or eliminating outliers (unusual or exceptional values).
- resolve data inconsistencies, using field knowledge or an expert's decision to resolve existing discrepancies.

The resulting data will be analyzed and used in the project by the applications developed to fulfil the KPIs of the VITAL-5G project. The KPIs are used to describe the optimized characteristics of the 5G network related to the implementation of the VITAL-5G project. The diagnosis of the 5G network is based on the collected data and the

main result obtained by analyzing the results of the project should be the description of the network properties achieved in the process of collected 5G-based data.

The results obtained in the VITAL-5G project are useful to better understand the 5G technology used in combination with the IoT data and the analysis of the provided data is useful in obtaining better results related to the T&L network. The data from the IoT sensors and cameras installed on the vessels is used to demonstrate the utility of the 5G network and of the developed applications used in the VITAL-5G project.

The two main types of test cases: Network-oriented Test Cases and Service-oriented Test Cases are useful in optimizing the VITAL-5G T&L network. The information gained through the VITAL-5G use cases provides both in-depth knowledge and best practices for data analysis. One of the main operations in the project it will be to connect data from various sources efficiently and structure the collected data to extract insights useful to the project.

Another step in the result analysis is the development of a roadmap to store, manage, and handle data internally, in the Cloud, and use analysis techniques to analyze the results in a fluid and functional manner. Very important in the process of results analysis methodology is the technology integration, or the integration of the decision support software with the technology. Based on the collected data and on the defined KPIs, insights will be built and these insights will be presented in a digestible, visual, interactive format (for example in a dashboard).

2.3.3 Manual and automatic reporting

The manual reporting used in the project will be used in pre-trials stage. The data will be obtained from CSV files and will be analyzed (by using methods described in Section 2.3.5) to assess the characteristics of the network and to analyze the network performance. The performance of the network will be verified and improved, if necessary, based on the results obtained from the manual reporting before the trials begin.

The outputs of the automatic reporting will be stored in Apache Kafka and will:

- a. Feed the Analytics and Diagnostics module, which will identify performance issues: detect anomalous behavior of one of the elements, based on the collected metrics; perform root cause analysis to identify the exact issues, etc.
- b. Be logged in Kafka to be used for the common KPIs analysis (see Section 2.3.5) to cross-compare among sites and offer global insights

2.3.4 Common and Trial/Service-specific KPIs

The resulting data will be saved in the Cloud platform provided by ORO, also hosting the main VITAL-5G platform, and afterwards, by feeding the Analytics and Diagnostics module, the 5G network will be characterized and the existing issues can be detected and fixed and its functionalities optimized. The defined KPIs should be derived by using the resulting data in the Cloud and the operations on this resulting data with the software developed.

Insights about the functionalities developed based on the 5G network will be found and the technologies used will generate data that will be gathered and analyzed to verify the performance of the respective T&L services. The T&L services will be verified from the operational point of view and the characteristic KPIs that need to be achieved should be based on the methodologies for data analysis, described above.

The measurement report template and all the other logged KPIs (both automatic and manual) will be based on the results analysis methodology described in Section 2.3.5.

2.3.5 Methods for data analysis

The following methods for data analysis will be used in the result analysis:

1. Descriptive analysis (what happened in the network).

The raw data is ordered, manipulated, and interpreted based on the various sources to turn it into valuable insights for the optimization of the T&L 5G networks. The process of performing descriptive analysis is essential

because it allows important information about the 5G networks to be presented in a useful manner. This analysis is useful in predicting future outcomes or answering questions on why the network behaves in certain ways (e.g., coverage gaps, Throughput peaks and dips, etc.), and it allows the data to be organized such that further investigations can be conducted.

2. Exploratory analysis (i.e., exploring data relationships)

It is used to explore the relationship between data and the variables. It enables to build connections and solutions to different problems related to the 5G T&L network.

3. Diagnostic analysis (i.e., why events happened in the 5G network)

The results will be used in diagnostic data analytics to understand the causes of potential degradation of performance and/or unexpected behavior. By using diagnostic analysis, the partners in the project will know why something happened as well as how it happened and which part of the end to end chain (e.g., network, server, NetApp, end-device) is responsible, and the exact measures to be taken to tackle the issue or challenge.

4. Predictive analysis (interpret what will happen)

Prescriptive data techniques or predictive analysis use patterns or trends to develop, practical strategies to respond to the events that will happen.

There are various methods for data analysis that can be used in the VITAL-5G project such as: cluster analysis, regression analysis, neural networks, data mining, time series analysis, decision trees, etc.

2.4 Experimenter consent forms & Questionnaires

In order to facilitate and streamline the experimentation process with the VITAL-5G platform and its associated facilities, the consortium members have created a standard consent form to be used by internal and external experimenters. This form will be used to provide legal coverage to the VITAL-5G project and facilities and inform the experimenters about the data that are being logged during the trials. Moreover, this form will be used as legal ground for the processing of personal information or whenever human subjects will participate in the experiments. This template was delivered as part of the deliverable VITAL5G D8.1 H-Requirements No. 1 [7] and contains the necessary information to inform the participants of the following topics

- What information will be gathered and why
- What this information will be used for by who
- What the rights of the participants are and how to execute them.

The template, as an example can be found in **Annex I: Consent form for trials**, will be adapted based on the experiment or questionnaire it will be used for, but the basic structure and content will remain the same.

3 Experimentation / Measurement framework

3.1 Common Data Format (CDF)

3.1.1 Automatic reporting

The Common Data Format (CDF) that we present in this section is a common format of presenting real-time or historical data to the monitoring system within the VITAL-5G platform. While executing experiments, each of the 5G testbeds from the three pilot sites is collecting various types of measurements, such as network, infrastructure, platform and service-related ones, which all result in a set of KPIs that need to be further analysed. In order to make it able to collect data from distributed pilot sites, the monitoring system is expecting data to be published on a particular topic, which is specific to vertical service and its ID (VSID<xx>), and also contains the information about the originating pilot site (i.e., Antwerp, Galati, or Athens), the type of the metric that is further described in Section 3.2, and the KPI itself (e.g., latency, and CPU load).

As shown in Figure 2, the common data format is simple and defined as a JSON object, which contains some mandatory fields (keys) that are common for all types of metrics (network, infrastructure, platform and service), such as *timestamp*, *value*, and *unit*. This way, the data from any pilot site can be i) collected in a unified manner, ii) processed by the monitoring system in an efficient way, and iii) exposed towards the other VITAL-5G platform elements such as Results Analytics or AI-based diagnostics, for further analysis. These mandatory fields are self-explanatory, as the *timestamp* defines the exact moment when the measurement was collected, the *value* defines the measured value of the metric, and *unit* should be the same for all measurements published on a specific topic, but in case it changes it is important to pass it to the monitoring system so that the data processing can be performed in a correct way (e.g., conversion from seconds to milliseconds). Nevertheless, there are also some fields that are mandatory, but specific for the type of metric, such as *networkSliceId* for network-related metrics (i.e., it is important to specify the slice for which the network KPI is collected), *VmId* for infrastructure and platform metrics (i.e., it is important to specify the VM for which the infrastructure or platform KPIs are collected), or *typeServiceID* to indicate the type of service for the service related metrics (i.e., the ID of the vertical service that belongs to specific pilot site, e.g., VS1).

Figure 2: Topic definition & common data format for collecting measurements from different sites.

More details about the monitoring system and the mechanisms of collecting data from distributed pilot sites will be provided in D2.3.

In Figure 3, we provide some examples of how data can be placed into the common data format, depending on the type of the metric.

Figure 3: Examples of fields in the common data format depending on the metric category.

3.1.2 Manual reporting

The format we present in this section is the common format of presenting manual data monitoring of the tests executed manually, referring to the 5G testbeds of the three sites. The manual reporting tests are oriented mainly to the Network and 5G services related KPIs, comprising sets of experiments executed at the 5G UE and Network level. All the manual aggregated KPIs are further analysed and evaluated. For this reporting, the data format is defined as .CSV format which contains mandatory fields common for the measured types of metrics (Test sequence, 5G network metrics, timestamps, values and units). Based on this, each of the testbed is able to collect all these manual data in a unified manner. In Table 2 we provide example of initial manual testing condition at the UE level, for the test sequence, time of measurement, network condition and testing experience results.

Table 2: Example of fields collected manually for initial UE setup

Test Sequence	Date / Time	Test methodology	UE IMSI test device	RAN Technology	Cell Name	Carrier bandwidth / System bandwidth
100	5/15/22 16:19	UE test device	22610300120162 5	5G	GA0039_NR_2	20 MHz
Service Access LAT Start	Service Access LON Start	Service Access Status / Network Reliability	User Experienced Downlink Data Rate (Mbps)	User Experienced Uplink Data Rate (Mbps)	E2E Latency (RTT / msec)	Jitter (msec)
46.08894	23.592573	SUCCESS / FAILED	345.02	148.02	6	3

Additional, manually collected metrics will be collected by each 5G-tetbed, prior to the execution of trials, in order to assist with the performance evaluation of the 5G networks themselves. Namely:

- In Table 3 we provide examples of UE manually tested KPIs and results, tested at the UE level during several evaluation rounds, as the aggregated results are also to be evaluated from this manual perspective in terms of reliability.
- In Table 4 we provide the example of network manual collection of the packet send vs received, to measure in this format the 5G network reliability, based on dropped/received report.
- In Table 5 we provide the example of the network manual collection and evaluation round for the network reliability KPIs.
- In Table 6 we provide the example format of the test sequences of the network bandwidth KPIs measured at the network level using traffic generator tools, such as Iperf.
- In Table 7 we provide an example of the format for the evaluation of the network bandwidth KPIs

Table 3: Example of fields format collected manually for the UE KPIs results

Evaluation	Reliability	Maximum expected latency	Guaranteed Network latency	DL peak troughput (Mbps)
evaluation rounds	nb of (Service Access Status SUCCESS test) nb of (total Service Access Status tests) %	max (UE E2E latency value results - msec)	min (UE E2E latency value results)	Max (User Experienced Downlink Data Rate results)
1	99.5	17	20	380
2	99.5	15	20	400
UL peak troughput (Mbps)	Application Guaranteed Downstream Data Rate (Mbps)	Application Guaranteed Ustream Data Rate (Mbps)	User Experienced Downlink Data Rate (Mbps)	User Experienced Uplink Data Rate (Mbps)
Max (User Experienced Uplink Data Rate results)	Min (User Experienced Downlink Data Rate results)	Min (User Experienced Uplink Data Rate results)	Average (User Experienced Downlink Data Rate results)	average (User Experienced Uplink Data Rate)
180	160	100	250	120
200	180	120	280	150

Table 4: Example of fields format collected manually for 5G network results

Date / Time	Cell Name	Reliability - Nb of packet sent	Reliability - Nb of packet dropped	Network reliability %
5/15/22 16:19	GA0039_NR_2	156897	1267	0.81%

Table 5: Example of fields format for network KPIs evaluation rounds

Evaluation rounds	Network reliability % (based on N6 physical interface RX/TX packet drops rate)
1	99.19%
2	

Table 6: Example of fields format for network bandwidths KPIs details

Test Sequence	Date / Time	Test methodology	Downstream throughput (Mbps)	Upstream throughput (Mbps)
25769803797	5/15/22 16:19	Iperf	320	180

Table 7: Example of fields format of the evaluation round of the network bandwidth KPIs

Evaluation rounds	Downstream throughput (Mbps)	Upstream throughput (Mbps)
1	Min (downstream throughput)	Min (upstream throughput)
2		

The proposed common format of the manual reporting is referring to the manual tests executed in the 5G testbeds accordingly to the testbeds manual measurement capabilities and reported as manual test in the proposed format, to be further evaluated in the VITAL-5G platform.

3.2 Common set of KPIs

In this Section, we present an overview of metrics that will be collected during the pilot trials, for each of the experiments associated to the testcases that are described in Section 4.2. Given the diversity of pilots in the project, as well as the presence of different 5G ecosystem components such as 5G radio and core network (jointly referred to as Network), NFV infrastructure for deploying services, VITAL-5G platform, and service that are designed and developed for each of the use cases, we made a thorough analysis of all types of metrics that are essential to collect and study towards testing and validating the performance of 5G-enhanced vertical services for ports and warehouses.

First, we define four different metric categories, depending on the scope of the overall 5G ecosystem to which they apply, i.e., network, infrastructure, platform, and service metrics. Each of these categories will be further studied in the respective subsections, including the overview of the exact metrics that belong to the specific category.

Second, for all metric categories, we create a common methodology of defining metrics (Figure 4), which consists of the metric type (Non-functional and Functional metrics), as well as parameters such as measurability, priority, description, testbed components, involved parties, measurement granularity, source, and measurement description.

Figure 4: Methodology of defining metrics in the Vital-5G.

The differentiation to Non-Functional and Functional metrics is defined with reference to ETSI MEC-IEG 006 [7]. In particular, Non-Functional metrics reflect the performance of deployment and management of vertical services (e.g., network, platform, infrastructure, and service configuration/management/orchestration), i.e., and these metrics do not directly affect the service performance that is experienced by end users (e.g., vessel, and AGV). On the other hand, Functional metrics are related to network/infrastructure/platform/service performance that has a direct impact on the users' perception. The assessment of measurability and priority is done per each metric. While measurability purely defines the level of complexity of measuring/determining a specific metric during the experiment execution, priority determines how essential a specific metric is for delivering vertical services to end users via 5G networks in the scope of the VITAL-5G project.

The overview of involved testbed components helps us to distinguish which components on a particular 5G testbed (Belgian, Romanian, and Greek) are involved in measuring the KPI (e.g., 5G RAN, 5G Core, Uplink classifier, UE, OSM, or NetApp), while involved parties are determined to keep track of the partners that are responsible for measuring a particular metric. The measurement granularity determines how often the metric is measured, i.e., either in real-time or non-real-time (historical data collected after an experiment is executed), also referring to time granularity, i.e., per second/minute/day. The measurement description is further described in testcases, where partners define a detailed procedure of performing tests and collecting respective relevant measurements.

3.2.1 Service oriented KPIs

In Table 8, we present a list of metrics that are common for all vertical services in all three use cases within the VITAL-5G project, i.e., Automated Vessel Transport (UC1), 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras (UC2), and Automation & remote operation of freight logistics (UC3).

For each of the metrics listed in Table 8, we define whether they are functional or non-functional, vertical-agnostic or vertical-specific, and we also provide a common definition. Afterwards, in Table 9, Table 10, and Table 11, we make a more detailed overview of all these metrics from a perspective of a particular vertical service belonging to one of the three use cases. Although all metrics presented in Table 8 are considered common for all services, they still might deviate in terms of interpretation (metric definition), and the assessment of their measurability and priority for a particular use case could also change.

Table 8: Service-oriented metrics: Functional (F), Non-Functional (NF).

Metric	F/NF	Type	Description
Average response time (end-to-end latency)	F	Vertical-agnostic	The average response time advertised for application clients' service requests. The time needed for a vertical service to produce a response based on the received input (request, or data).
Quality of experience	F	Vertical-agnostic	5G PPP definition: Measured at the UE side at application or application API level. ETSI definition: Efficiency, ease of use, reliability, customer loyalty, are some of the factors the QoE addresses. In addition to these, other aspects such as service costs, architecture security and user's privacy can be taken into account for a more comprehensive definition of QoE.
Availability	F	Vertical-agnostic	Advertised percentage of time the services are available for use.
Connection bandwidth	F	Vertical-agnostic	The required connection bandwidth in Kbit/s for the vertical services.
Service continuity support	F	Vertical-agnostic	Indicates if service continuity support is required or not for the application.
Localization accuracy	F	Service-specific	Definition specific for a service type.
Precision of object detection	F	Service-specific	Definition specific for a service type.
Scalability	NF	Vertical-agnostic	Indicates if service is designed to accommodate different numbers of UEs, volumes of input data, etc. Scalability of service could be tested through the number of requests that it could process simultaneously, where the request can come either from UEs that are connected to the service, or from the other services that are interfacing with it.

Table 9: Service-oriented metrics for vertical services in UC1 (BE): Vertical service (VS), Measurability (M), Priority (P), Low (L), High (H), Medium (M).

VS	Metric	M	P	Testbed components	Partners involved	Description
Vessel autonomous control & Remote vessel monitoring	Average response time (end-to-end latency)	H	H	BE testbed, overall response time measured at client side (vessel), computational delay measured at server side (NetApp infrastructure)	IMEC, Seafar, Telenet	The average time needed for a service to derive a navigable path for vessel, and to send it to the captain on-board.
	Quality of experience	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Availability	H	H	BE testbed, all testbed components / measured at server side (monitoring dashboard)	IMEC, Seafar	Percentage of time the route information, including map, obstacles and path suggestions are available on the captain monitoring dashboard.
	Connection bandwidth	H	H	BE testbed, all testbed components / measured at server side and vessel side	IMEC, Seafar, Telenet	Bandwidth available for sending data from the vessel, for sending obstacle information from the digital twin, for data exchange between the autonomous navigation planner and the monitoring, for data exchange between the monitoring and the speed optimizer, for data exchange between data collection and all the other NetApps.
	Service continuity support	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Localization accuracy	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Precision of object detection	L	H	Digital Twin / measured and stored at server side (monitoring dashboard)	IMEC, Seafar	Measures how accurate the LiDAR data/occupancy grid map is. If the LiDAR often claims there is an object even though there is not, this metric will be low.
	Scalability	M	M	NA	NA	NA

Table 10: Service-oriented metrics for vertical services in UC2 (RO): Vertical service (VS), Measurability (M), Priority (P), Low (L), High (H), Medium (M).

VS	Metric	M	P	Testbed components	Partners involved	Description
Data-enabled assisted navigation	Average response time (end-to-end latency)	H	H	RO testbed, response time measured at client side (vessel), computational delay measured at server side (NetApp infrastructure)	BEIA, ORO, NAV, ATG	The average time needed for the service to provide warnings and rapid events classification, from the time it receives the sensing data and/or video stream.
	Quality of experience	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Availability	H	H	RO testbed, all testbed components / measured at server side (monitoring dashboard)		Percentage of time the warnings and event classification are available on the captain monitoring dashboard.
	Connection bandwidth	H	H	RO testbed, all testbed components / measured at server side and vessel side	BEIA, ORO, NAV, ATG	Bandwidth available for sending sensing data from the vessel, for sending video streams, for providing accurate warnings, for providing classified events, for data exchange between data collection and all the other NetApps.
	Service continuity support	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Localization accuracy	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Scalability	M	M	NA	NA	NA
Accurate electronic navigation maps creation	Average response time (end-to-end latency)	H	H	RO testbed, response time measured at client side (vessel), processing delay measured at server side (NetApp infrastructure)	BEIA, ORO, NAV	The average time needed for the service to correctly estimate the safe distance, from the time it receives the distributed sensing data (time needed to ingest, fuse and post-process data).
	Quality of experience	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Availability	H	H	RO testbed, all testbed		Percentage of time the safe distance is correctly

				components / measured at server side (monitoring dashboard)		estimated and is available on the captain monitoring dashboard.
	Connection bandwidth	H	H	RO testbed, all testbed components / measured at server side and vessel side	BEIA, ORO, NAV	Bandwidth available for sending sensing data from the vessel, for sending other external data, for providing correct safe distance estimation, for data exchange between data collection and all the other NetApps.
	Service continuity support	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Localization accuracy	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Precision of object detection	L	H	Video cameras, depth sensor / measured and stored at server side (monitoring dashboard)	BEIA, ORO, NAV	Measures how accurate the safe distance is estimated from video stream and sensing data. If the post-processing module often claims objects are close/farther than real, this metric will be low.
	Scalability	M	M	NA	NA	NA
Predictive maintenance and sanity checks applied on the sensor data for ship safety purposes	Average response time (end-to-end latency)	H	H	RO testbed, response time measured at client side (vessel), processing delay measured at server side (NetApp infrastructure)	BEIA, ORO, NAV, INCE	The average time needed for the service to provide predictions/forecasts and decisions, from the time it receives the distributed sensing data (time needed to ingest, fuse, post-process data).
	Quality of experience	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Availability	H	H	RO testbed, all testbed components / measured at server side (monitoring dashboard)		Percentage of time the decisions are available on the captain monitoring dashboard.
	Connection bandwidth	H	H	RO testbed, all testbed components / measured at server side and vessel side	BEIA, ORO, NAV, INCE	Bandwidth available for sending sensing data from the vessel, for sending other external data, for providing predictions/forecasts, for providing decisions.
	Service	L	L	NA	NA	NA

	continuity support					
	Localization accuracy	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Precision of object detection	L	H	Video cameras, sensors / measured and stored at server side (monitoring dashboard)	BEIA, ORO, NAV, INCE	Measures how accurate the automated labelling, outlier detection, trace back analysis, graphical representations, predictions/forecasts for the near-future are. If the AI/ML mechanisms do not have regularly pre-trained models, this metric will be low.
	Scalability	M	M	NA	NA	NA

Table 11: Service-oriented metrics for vertical services in UC3 (GR): Vertical service (VS), Measurability (M), Priority (P), Low (L), High (H), Medium (M).

VS	Metric	M	P	Testbed components	Partners involved	Description
Autonomous pallet transport within the warehouse	Average response time (end-to-end latency)	H	H	DIA testbed, response time as measured by the AGV (client), delay measured at server	WINGS	The time needed for the service to “translate” a pick pallet request to a target, send the request and for the robot to activate its motors.
	Quality of experience	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Availability	H	M	DIA testbed, service availability measured by the server	WINGS	Table 8
	Connection bandwidth	H	M	DIA testbed, measured by the server	WINGS	Table 8
	Service continuity support	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Localization accuracy	L	H	DIA testbed, measured by the AGV (client)	WINGS	The proximity of the robot position in the map to the actual robot position in reality.
	Precision of object detection	M	H	DIA testbed, measured by the AGV (client)	WINGS	How close the AGV actually comes to an obstacle per service iteration.
	Scalability	L	L	NA	NA	NA

Follow-me function for human-robot collaboration	Average response time (end-to-end latency)	L	L	NA	WINGS	No request is made by the UE and no response is sent by the robot to it.
	Quality of experience	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Availability	H	H	DIA testbed, service availability measured by the server.	WINGS	Table 8
	Connection bandwidth	H	M	DIA testbed, measured by the server	WINGS	Table 8
	Service continuity support	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Localization accuracy	L	H	DIA testbed, measured by the AGV (client).	WINGS	The proximity of the robot position in the map to the actual robot position in reality.
	Precision of object detection	M	H	DIA testbed, measured by the AGV (client).	WINGS	How close the AGV actually comes to an obstacle per service iteration.
	Scalability	L	L	NA	NA	NA
Remote monitoring and control of AGVs	Average response time (end-to-end latency)	H	H	DIA testbed, measured by the AGV (client).	WINGS	Table 8
	Quality of experience	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Availability	H	H	DIA testbed, service availability measured by the server.	WINGS	Table 8
	Connection bandwidth	H	H	DIA testbed, measured by the server.	WINGS	Table 8
	Service continuity support	L	L	NA	NA	NA
	Localization accuracy	L	L	DIA testbed, measured by the AGV (client)	WINGS	The proximity of the robot position in the map to the actual robot position in reality.
	Precision of object detection	M	M	DIA testbed, measured by the AGV (client).	WINGS	How close the AGV actually comes to an obstacle per service iteration.
	Scalability	M	M	DIA testbed, measured by the NetApp (server)	WINGS	Table 8

3.2.2 Platform oriented KPIs

Under the umbrella of platform-oriented KPIs, we define the list of metrics that reflect on the performance of management and orchestration operations, and study how their performance affects the performance of vertical services. In Table 12, there is a list of platform metrics that we consider common for all three pilot sites, and since all three 5G testbeds are leveraging on the same management and orchestration solution, i.e., Open Source MANO (OSM), the assessment of measurability and priority remains the same for all three sites.

Table 12: Platform-oriented metrics: Functional (F), Non-Functional (NF), Measurability (M), Priority (P).

Metric	NF/F	M	P	Testbed components	Partners involved	Description
On-boarding delay	NF	H	M	OSM	IMEC, NXW, WINGS, ORO	Delay of on-boarding application package (e.g., descriptor, Docker container image, etc.) in all computing nodes.
Runtime orchestration delay	NF	H	M	OSM	IMEC, NXW, WINGS, ORO	The overall time needed for orchestration elements to perform any LCM operation on the selected service. This includes instantiation, scaling, relocation, and termination of services.
Context-update time	NF	M	L	OSM	IMEC, WINGS, ORO	Delay of updating the context of a deployed service during its runtime.
Resource footprint	NF	H	M	5G testbed, VM level	IMEC, WINGS, ORO	Resource footprint required to deploy the platform; The maximum number of VNFs a MANO system can effectively/efficiently monitor and manage. Feature palette (e.g., support for DevOps, VNF Package Management, VNF image management, integrated monitoring system).
Service-placement delay	NF	M	H	Placement service	IMEC, NXW, WINGS, ORO	The time needed for orchestration entities to make a decision on the placement of service.

3.2.3 Network oriented KPIs

Based on network tests one can extract several generic functional KPIs at network and at slice level. By setting up probes in different points of the flow from the UE to the core, one can review KPIs on UE side, at the UPF Data Network Interface and also in various points of the RAN and Core. The VITAL-5G testbed owners have agreed on a common set of network KPIs that will be measured across all three testbeds of VITAL-5G, to facilitate the extraction of common insights, which are reported in Table 13.

Table 13: VITAL-5G common network KPIs

Metric	NF/ F	M	P	Testbed components	Partners involved	Description
Minimum UL throughput	F	H	M	UPF/IP Network	ORO, OTE, TEL	UE transmitting IP packets to the N6 interface.
Minimum DL throughput	F	H	M	UPF/IP Network	ORO, OTE, TEL	UE receiving IP packets from the N6 interface.
Maximum latency	F	H	M	UPF Data Network Interface	ORO, OTE, TEL	5G PPP definition: RTT of UE IP packets transmitted to the N6 interface.
Network reliability	F	M	M	UPF Data Network Interface	ORO, OTE, TEL	5G PPP definition: Transport layer packets are lost between the UE and the N6 interface.
UL peak throughput	F	H	M	UE	ORO, OTE, TEL	5G PPP definition: Single UE transmitting IP packets to the N6 interface.
DL peak throughput	F	H	M	UE	ORO, OTE, TEL	5G PPP definition: Single UE receiving IP packets from the N6 interface
User Experienced Downlink Data Rate	F	H	H	RAN/Core/Infra	ORO, OTE, TEL	Downlink data rate as perceived at the application layer. It corresponds to the amount of application data (bits) correctly sent within a certain time window
User Experienced Uplink Data Rate	F	H	H	RAN/Core/Infra	ORO, OTE, TEL	Downlink data rate as perceived at the application layer. It corresponds to the amount of application data (bits) correctly sent within a certain time window
Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR)	F	H	H	RAN/Core/Infra	ORO, OTE, TEL	Percentage value of the amount of sent network layer packets successfully delivered to a given system entity within the time constraint required by the targeted service, divided by the total number of sent network layer packets
Packet Loss	F	H	H	RAN/Core/Infra	ORO, OTE, TEL	Percentage of the amount of sent network layer packets failed to be delivered to a given system entity within the time constraint required by the targeted service, divided by the total number of sent network layer packets
Application Guaranteed Data Rate	F	H	M	NA	ORO, OTE, TEL	Guaranteed bit rate for the application to function correctly
Coverage area	F	H	H	NA	ORO, OTE, TEL	The geographic area within which the Mobile Network Operator voice/data services can be accessed and used by the subscriber
Reliability	F/N F	H	M	NA	ORO, OTE, TEL	The amount of application layer messages or network layer packets (depending on the measurement level) successfully delivered to a given system node within the time constraint required by the targeted service, divided by the total number of sent messages or packets

System Bandwidth	F	H	H	NA	ORO, OTE, TEL	Maximum aggregated system bandwidth including frequency guard bands.
E2E Latency	F	H	H	UE	ORO, OTE, TEL	The time required from the moment a data packet is transmitted by the source application, to the moment it is received by the destination application.
Guaranteed Network Latency	F/N F	H	H	UE	ORO, OTE, TEL	The guaranteed maximum time required from the moment a data packet is transmitted by the source to packet gateway
Jitter	F	H	H		ORO, OTE, TEL	The variation in the latency on a packet flow between two systems. Jitter can be caused by network congestion, timing drift and route changes
Dropped packets per second	F	H	H	UPF	ORO, OTE, TEL	UPF IP dropped packets detected minute by minute. The number of packets is obtained by combining packets direction (Ingress/Egress) and space where the process is performed (kernel or user space).
Forwarded packets per second	F	H	H	UPF	ORO, OTE, TEL	UPF IP forwarded packets. The number of packets is obtained by combining packets direction (Ingress/Egress), space where the process is performed (kernel or user space).
Dropped bytes per second	F	H	H	UPF	ORO, OTE, TEL	Number of dropped bytes per second as measured in the UPF
Forwarded bytes per second	F	H	H	UPF	ORO, OTE, TEL	Number of forwarded bytes per second as measured in the UPF

3.2.4 Infrastructure oriented KPIs

The infrastructure-oriented KPIs (Table 14) are defined to determine the computational/memory/disk load imposed on the RAN, Core, and NFV infrastructure (servers with NetApps), while running vertical services in all three use cases within the VITAL-5G project. For each of the metrics, we make an evaluation of measurability and performance that are currently defined in the same way for all three pilot sites and will be further re-assessed once the results for all three sites are collected during the execution of pilot trials. In addition, the testbed components involved in measuring the KPI are listed in Table 14.

Table 14: Infrastructure-oriented metrics: Functional (F), Non-Functional (NF), Measurability (M), Priority (P).

Metric	NF/F	M	P	Testbed components	Partners involved	Description
CPU load	NF	H	H	NetApps, VMs	Testbed & NetApp owners	Average CPU usage during platform operations (e.g., on-boarding NetApp, processing orchestration requests, performing LCM operations).
Memory load	NF	H	H	NetApps, VMs	Testbed & NetApp owners	Average memory usage during platform operations (e.g., on-boarding NetApp,

						processing orchestration requests, performing LCM operations).
Disk usage	NF	H	M	NetApps VMs	Testbed & NetApp owners	Current disk usage at the VM where the NetApp is running.
Compute load/infra load	NF	H	H	NetApps VMs	Testbed & NetApp owners	Compute load and Infrastructure load during platform operations reported to the total available pool of resources.
GPU load	NF	H	H	NetApps VMs	Testbed & NetApp owners	Average GPU usage during NetApp operations (e.g., AI/ML, video processing).

3.3 Measurement reporting template

Besides the automatic and manual processes for reporting trial output from the experiments with a common format, that have been described in the previous sections, a process for each experimenter to report the detailed post-processed results of each of the defined Testcases is also necessary. These results will be the outcome of the detailed post-processing of the measurements collected during the execution of each of the Testcases and will be used for the final evaluation and validation of each of the Testcases (TC) (as described in Section 4.2) and correspondingly of each of the Services and NetApps the testcase addresses.

In order to facilitate the proper result collection, post-processing and eventual evaluation of each testcase, a common Measurement Reporting Template (MRT) has been agreed among the VITAL-5G partners, which is depicted in Figure 5. The VITAL-5G partners (and 3rd party experimenters) will use this template to report on the outcomes of each of the defined Testcases, and to document the relevant metrics/KPIs.

Test Case (TC) ID				
Test Case (TC) Name				
Test UE Info				
<i>UE Type: Mobile Phone/ Tablet</i>				
<i>UE category</i>				
<i>UE SW version</i>				
<i>UE speed</i>				
Test Variables				
<i>Indicate any condition that could have an impact on the test result and any possible deviation compared to the test case description.</i>				
TC Results Report				
Number of repetitions	3			
TC comments	<i>Add here any main observations</i>			
Tools used	<i>Tools used (ex. iperf, speedtest) and relevant parameters of execution</i>			
TC Logs	<i>Provide name of the file or data in a separate sheet</i>			
Test Results	Iteration #1	Iteration #2	Iteration #3	Descriptions/Diagrams
<Metric1 measured>				<i>Reference Figures provided below and explain measurements; if necessary expand to separate sheet. But a brief result conclusion should be added here, especially if to lead in further enhancements</i>
<Metric2 measured>				
<Average Metric measured>				
TC Responsible	<i>Partners involved</i>			
Date	<i>Date of execution of the reported measure</i>			

Figure 5: VITAL-5G common Measurement Reporting Template

The MRT is comprised of several fields that enable the full traceback of the results presented to a specific Testcase and trialling scenario, while each of the MRTs is strictly linked to one of the defined Testcases (see Section 4.2). More specifically the VITAL-5G MRT is comprised of the following fields:

- **Testcase ID:** This field uniquely links the MRT with one of the defined Testcases. The results reported in the particular MRT belong to the TC with this specific ID
- **Testcase name:** The full name of the linked TC for ease of use.
- **Test UE Info:** This field contains the details of the User Equipment (UE) (smartphone, tablet, device, etc.) that was used to collect the measurements reported in this MRT. In that way, the results reported in the MRT are not simply linked to a specific TC but are also linked to specific devices and SW versions, thus guaranteeing the traceability and repeatability of the experiments.
- **Test Variables:** This field allows for the recording of additional test variables that may affect the results / measurements and may not be recorded in the TC itself. This could be environmental factors (e.g., heavy rain during testing, heavy traffic of other vehicles obstructing Line of Sight (LoS), etc.) or simply additional variables that may not have been part of the original TC description (e.g., last minute change of equipment due to malfunction, etc.).
- **TC Results Report:** This field is used to record meta-data regarding the experiment such as the number of test repetitions, the tools used to collect information or introduce traffic, the format and measurement points of the logs used to provide the metrics/KPIs, etc.
- **Test Results:** The fields comprising this section are used to report the actual measurements and the results of the corresponding post-processing (figures, diagrams, etc.). This section is editable and may be adapted to the needs of the specific experiment, i.e., add rows to accommodate multiple KPIs, add columns to accommodate multiple iterations, etc. This section also contains the results of the post

processing of the collected values (average, max/min values, etc.), as well as the experimenters' comments and conclusions (Description section).

- TC responsible: This field contains the name/ID of the experimenter so it can always be traced-back to them, for clarifications and accountability.
- Date: This field contains the date of the experiment execution.

Even though the three VITAL-5G experimentation facilities address different T&L environments and evaluate different UCs and NetApps, the common reporting template will streamline the reporting and evaluation processes across the entire project. In this way, it will be more intuitive for any experimenter/reader to read and understand the VITAL-5G measurement and evaluation reports and will facilitate the analysis of the 5G added value for the entire T&L sector. The MRTs, along with the automatic (json format) and manual (CSV format) KPI reporting described in Section 3.2, will constitute the main input of Task 4.4 (Analysis and Evaluation) and of deliverables D4.2 (M33) and D4.3 (M35), which will provide the final analysis of the VITAL-5G trialling results and the gained insights.

The common measurement reporting template is openly available to all VITAL-5G partners via the project's cloud-based document sharing platform (Teamwork) and will become available to 3rd party experimenters as soon as their experimentation cycles begin.

4 VITAL-5G Facilities Trials

4.1 VITAL-5G facilities trials planning

The purpose of the VITAL-5G trial planning is to plan the various phases of testing, trialling, results analysis and re-design necessary to successfully complete the VITAL-5G trials and NetApps evaluation. This plan takes also into account the 3rd party experimentation activities in each of the trial sites and is built around the various milestones and deliverables of the project, ensuring that the trial results will be available on time for delivery. The trial plans of the three trial sites have been created using the same template and guidelines and are based on eight different stages that all trial sites will go through. Table 15 provides the definition of the eight stages that have been used to create the VITAL-5G trial plans at each facility.

Table 15: VITAL-5G Trialling stages definition

Stage #	Stage Name	Stage Definition
S1	Development/Lab tests	Development/upgrades period instantiating the required UC functions and testing locally (e.g., labs) in order to finalize or improve the functionality. These tests do NOT take place in the actual trial site to be used for the full trials (i.e., ports, warehouse)
S2	Dry Runs	Mature tests performed to evaluate the performance of 2 or more integrated functions/components or even the end-to-end targeted functionality. The goal of these tests is NOT to collect KPIs for evaluation, but rather as a readiness check/verification of proper functionality. These tests could take place either in a lab or the actual trial site environment.
S3	Full trials	Full trials performed exclusively in the targeted trial environment (ports, warehouse), according to the defined Test Cases. These tests are aimed at collecting metrics/KPIs to be used for the evaluation of performance and UC/NetApp validation.
S4	Results Analysis & Evaluation	Results analysis phase, where the collected metrics from stage S3 are processed to gain insights and draw conclusions on the performance of the SUT. This stage can feedback its results to previous stages of development and testing and initiate a new cycle of tests/trials, based on upgraded functionality or updated test cases.
S5	3rd party onboarding	Interaction period with 3rd party experimenters during which the trial site / project partners assist with the onboarding of 3rd party experimenters and the preparation of their experiments (e.g., training days, instructions, deployment, set-up and configuration, of 3rd party NetApps and/or devices for their trials)
S6	3rd party trials	Full trials performed by 3rd party experimenters (with the support of VITAL-5G partners) to evaluate their targeted NetApp/service over the VITAL-5G platform and trial sites.
S7	3rd party Results Analysis & Evaluation	Results analysis phase, where the collected metrics of 3rd party experimenters from stage S6 are processed to gain insights and draw conclusions on the performance of their NetApp/Service.
S8	Demos	Demonstration event at the targeted trial environment (ports, warehouse) to showcase the achieved functionality / performance , with the presence of external consortium guests (e.g., PO, reviewers, industry partners)

Trial sites are allowed to add additional ad-hoc stages that they feel are needed to provide the detailed picture of their trial plans, which may not apply to the rest of the sites. The rest of this section, provides the detailed trial

planning of each of the three facilities of VITAL-5G, according to the best estimations of the experts at the time of writing of this deliverable.

4.1.1 BE facility trial planning

The trial planning of the BE facility has been based on (i) the timelines provided by the network operator (TEL) regarding the availability of the E2E 5G SA network, (ii) the timelines provided by the vessel operator (SF) regarding the availability of the vessel and of the 5G SA network equipment on board, (iii) the project planning (Gantt) which translates to the work plan of the various WPs and Tasks that will deliver the various components (NetApps, experimentation tools, platform functions, etc.) that will enable the BE trials and (iv) the estimated time needed for the various integration and testing activities that will deliver the final operational BE facility. The BE facility trial planning also takes into account the various significant milestones and deliverables of the project (e.g., reviews, demos, 3rd party experimentation, etc.). To build the planning, it was decided to allocate a sufficient number of dry runs, with an alternance of development/lab tests. Due to vessel availabilities, full trials require to be decided several months ahead. At the time of writing of this deliverable, one such trial period was scheduled, followed by a results & analysis period, but later ones may be added depending on needs. A focus was put on 3rd party trials and their corresponding results & analysis periods. As such, various configurations, features and re-designs will be able to be tested, before arriving at the optimum solutions. Figure 6 and Figure 7 below depict the BE facility trial planning for the years 2022 and 2023 respectively.

4.1.2 GR facility trial planning

The trial planning of the GR facility has been based on (i) the deployment timelines provided by the testbed owner (OTE) regarding the availability of the E2E 5G SA network, (ii) the project planning (Gantt) which translates to the work plan of the various WPs and Tasks that will deliver the various components (NetApps, experimentation tools, platform functions, etc.) that will enable the GR trials and (iii) the estimated time needed for the various integration and testing activities that will deliver the final operational GR facility. The GR facility trial planning also takes into account the various significant milestones and deliverables of the project (e.g., reviews, demos, 3rd party experimentation, etc.). The planning follows the known experimentation cycle which is: trial → results analysis & evaluation → configuration change or solution upgrade → testing & integration → trial. As such, various configurations, features and re-designs will be able to be tested, before arriving at the optimum solutions. Figure 8 and Figure 9 below depict the GR facility trial planning for the years 2022 and 2023 respectively.

4.1.3 RO facility trial planning

The trial planning of the RO facility has been based on (i) the deployment timelines provided by the testbed owner (ORO) regarding the availability of the E2E 5G SA network, (ii) the timelines provided by the vessel operator (NAV) regarding the availability of the vessel and of the 5G SA network equipment on board, (iii) the project planning (Gantt) which translates to the work plan of the various WPs and Tasks that will deliver the various components (NetApps, experimentation tools, platform functions, etc.) that will enable the RO trials and (iv) the estimated time needed for the various integration and testing activities that will deliver the final operational RO facility. The RO facility trial planning also takes into account the various significant milestones and deliverables of the project (e.g., reviews, demos, 3rd party experimentation, etc.). To build the planning, it was decided to allocate a sufficient number of weeks, with an alternance of development/lab tests. As such, various configurations, features and re-designs will be able to be tested, before arriving at the optimum solutions. Figure 10 and Figure 11 below depict the RO facility trial planning for the years 2022 and 2023 respectively.

Figure 6: BE Facility trial planning for the year 2022

Figure 7: BE facility Trial planning for the year 2023

Figure 8: GR Facility trial planning for the year 2022

Figure 9: GR facility Trial planning for the year 2023

Figure 10: RO Facility trial planning for the year 2022

Figure 11: RO facility Trial planning for the year 2023

4.2 Targeted testcases

4.2.1 Service oriented Testcases

This section provides the details about all the experiments that have been planned to be performed in the three VITAL-5G facilities, in order to collect data and evaluate the 5G network and NetApps performance. The Testcase (TC) template defined in D1.4 [3] has been used as a basis to document the details of each experiment. Each of the three experimentation facilities have defined their own list of TCs that will allow them to fully evaluate their respective T&L services and NetApps. It is highlighted, that this section only covers the service-oriented TCs which are meant to evaluate the service-level performance. The network-oriented TCs meant to evaluate the 5G network performance of each testbed are discussed in Section 4.2.2.

Third party experimenters may use these TCs as examples on how to properly define an experiment over the VITAL-5G platform, in an end-to-end fashion.

4.2.1.1 BE facility Testcases

In this subsection we provide an overview of the service-oriented test cases defined for the Automated Vessel Transport (BE) use case.

Test cases in the service-oriented category are organized according to each NetApp of the BE use case. For most NetApps they were defined by isolating functionalities that require a limited number of other NetApps. In this way the test cases span the successive levels of NetApps integration. The overview of the BE site service-oriented test cases are provided in Table 16, while Table 17 provides the overview of the custom service level KPIs used for the evaluation of the BE UC. An example of full test case description can be found in [Annex II](#).

All the BE facility service-oriented Testcases can be found on Teamwork².

Table 16: Service-oriented test cases - Antwerp (BE) facility

TC_ID	TC Title	TC Description/Goal/Focus
TC01_BE_S_VS6	Voyage planning	Autonomous navigation from point A to point B. Several settings: 1) straight line to close goal, no obstacles; 2) goal hidden after corner or challenging channel configuration; no obstacles. The focus is on correctness of the planning from start to goal in realistic situations without obstacles. Computation time is not taken into consideration here. This test requires the following NetApps: VS5, VS8.
TC02_BE_S_VS6	Obstacle avoidance	Obstacle avoidance from point A to point B. Several settings: 1) Unique fix obstacle (bridge pillar) on straight trajectory from A to B; 2) Several non-static obstacles on straight trajectory from A to B. The focus is on correctness of the obstacle avoidance in realistic situations. Computation time is not taken into consideration here. This test requires the following NetApps: VS5, VS8, VA5.
TC03_BE_S_VS6	Computation time for planning	Real-time planning. Several non-static obstacles on straight trajectory from point A to point B. The focus is on assessing computation time in a realistic situation and not on correctness of the planning.
TC04_BE_S_VS6	Request for takeover	Request for takeover (requires VS5, VS8, VA5): situation where no trajectory is possible (forced planning failure).
TC01_BE_S_VA5	Single LiDAR pre-processing	The LiDAR clustering should cluster the riverbanks and objects correctly.

² <https://inlecom.eu.teamwork.com/#/projects/1825878/files?catid=1824943>

TC02_BE_S_VA5	Single LiDAR occupancy grid map creation	The generated occupancy grid map should contain all obstacles detected by the LiDAR.
TC03_BE_S_VA5	Multiple LiDAR pre-processing	LiDAR data of three different LiDAR s should be fused correctly and cluster objects.
TC04_BE_S_VA5	Multiple LiDAR occupancy grid map creation	The generated occupancy grid map should contain all obstacles detected by the three LiDARs
TC01_BE_S_VS7_VS8	VS7: data receival from VS5	This test case consists in verifying the reception of data from VS5. In particular, the planning data (i.e., the voyage destination and timing) should be received correctly.
TC01_BE_S_VS7_VS5	VS7: data receival from VS8	This test case consists in verifying the reception of data from VS8. In particular, the current location of the vessel (i.e., the latitude and longitude) should be received correctly.
TC01_BE_S_VS7	Waiting time reduction	This test case consists in evaluating the waiting time reduction for a vessel (at the voyage destination).
TC02_BE_S_VS8	Exposing collected data towards other NetApps	VS8 should process the collected data and expose it towards other NetApps in a timely manner
TC01_BE_S_VS5	Real time Sensor updates	Sensor value real time updates
TC02_BE_S_VS5	UX Remote monitoring	The captain should easily be able to view all sensors and interact with the remote monitoring tool
TC01_BE_S_VS5_VS8	GPS visualization remote monitoring	Captain should be able to see real time position of the vessel on a map
TC01_BE_S_VS5_VS7	Optimal speed visualization in dashboard	The captain receives the optimal navigation speed in a timely manner in his dashboard

Table 17: Custom service level KPIs used for the BE facility Testcases

KPI ID	KPI name	Explanation	Scenarios
BE_VS6_KPI_1	Planning time	Difference between timestamps at receival of new output and timestamps at receival of new input.	The current vessel position, goal position and dynamic map are processed, and the output sent to monitoring in a sailing-compatible manner. Timestamps are logged at input and output times.
BE_VA5_KPI_1	Precision of object detection	This measures how accurately the LiDAR data/occupancy grid map is. If the LiDAR often believes there is an object even though there isn't, it will be low.	One scenario: Camera and Lidar data are recorded. Afterwards, it will be manually processed, and the precision will be calculated.

BE_VA5_KPI_2	Recall of object detection	This measures how well the LiDAR data/occupancy grid map contains all obstacles. If the LiDAR often misses obstacles, it will be low.	One scenario: Camera and Lidar data are recorded. Afterwards, it will be manually processed, and the recall will be calculated.
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4.2.1.2 GR facility Testcases

As part of the internal experimentation to be carried out at the Athens (GR) facility of VITAL-5G, the involved partners (WINGS, DIA, OTE) have planned all the relevant experiments that would allow for a thorough investigation and evaluation of the envisioned AGV based services over 5G connectivity at the DIA warehouse in Apsropyrgos, Athens. As mentioned in deliverable D2.1 [4] the GR site facility will instantiate three different AGV-based services within the warehouse based on the development of three NetApps, namely VA1, VS1 and VS2. In order to thoroughly evaluate the performance of the three provided services as well as that of the respective NetApps, nine (9) Testcases have been defined to be executed during the GR trials at the DIA warehouse. Table 18 provides the overview of these nine Testcases. The goal of these testcases is to evaluate the performance on a Service level and to establish whether the provided 5G network connectivity can accommodate the envisioned services. The network level performance will be evaluated based on the network-oriented testcases presented in Section 4.2.2.

Table 18: Service Oriented Testcases of the GR facility

TC_ID	TC Title	TC Description/Goal/Focus
TC01_GR_S	Pre-trial tests to ensure correct functionality of AGV and platform	Test localization, accuracy, LiDAR operation, integration, connection to platform and exchange of data, etc. test behaviour in case AGV is unable to properly complete an assigned task for any reason (obstacle in target unloading location, obstacle not allowing proper loading, low battery, etc.)
TC02_GR_S	<u>AGV based autonomous pallet transfer</u> : From inbound dock to designated storage location	For the AGV to successfully read the barcode on the pallet, to interact with WMS to identify the proper location, to navigate to the proper location avoiding obstacles, to identify empty spot in targeted location and to successfully deposit the pallet.
TC03_GR_S	<u>AGV based autonomous pallet transfer</u> : From end-of-picking point to designated checking station	For the AGV to receive command from worker that picking has finished, to interact with WMS to receive info on proper checking station, to navigate to said checking station and to deposit the pallet on an empty slot.
TC04_GR_S	<u>AGV based autonomous pallet transfer</u> : From checking station to designated outbound dock	For the AGV to receive command from worker regarding the ID of the pallet which is ready to be transported, the AGV to recognize the correct pallet and properly load it, to retrieve relevant info from the WMS, to transport it to the outbound dock and to deposit it at the appropriate empty spot.
TC05_GR_S	<u>Human-Robot collaboration</u> : follow worker based on beacons	For the AGV to engage in “follow-me” mode and to track and follow the designated worker, based on the TeraBee beacons. The AGV should stay at the designated distance from the worker and not lose him. Once the picking operation is finished, the AGV will transport the order picked to the appropriate checking station.

TC06_GR_S	<i>Human-Robot collaboration</i> : find far-away worker to follow	For the AGV to be summoned by a worker anywhere in the warehouse using the platform GUI, and to autonomously navigate to that worker. Once it is in close proximity to the worker to engage in “follow-me” mode and to assist with the picking operation.
TC07_GR_S	<i>Remote monitoring & Control of AGV</i> : Remote command to go to any point in the warehouse	For the AGV to receive a remote command from a user (UE) to go to a specific location in the warehouse (point A). The user will be able to monitor the entire process with a live feed of the on-board camera and the steady cam ³ , as well as the feed from the various onboard sensors.
TC08_GR_S	<i>Remote monitoring & Control of AGV</i> : Remote command to pick up pallet X from point A and teleoperate AGV to deliver it to point B	For the AGV to receive a remote command from a user (UE) to go to a specific location in the warehouse (point A), load a pallet and autonomously transfer it to another location (point B). The user will be able to monitor the entire process with a live feed of the on-board camera and the steady cam ³ , as well as the feed from the various onboard sensors.
TC09_GR_S	<i>Remote monitoring & Control of AGV</i> : Remote access to AGV camera and sensor feed	To test the video quality (and sensor quality) in terms of lost packets, video stream, Experience of user, throughout the entire warehouse, to find blackspots, etc.

Each of the Testcases described in Table 18, have been defined in detail using the common VITAL-5G Testcase template that was defined in deliverable D1.4 [3]. In this description, all the necessary details for each experiment are recorded that will ensure the traceability and replicability of each experiment/test and will ensure that all the angles of the experimentation process have been thought out. Some of these details include the experiment route, the functional and non-functional requirements, the recorded KPIs, the metrics processing methodology and more.

As each filled-in Testcase is about 4-5 pages long, it would be unpractical to include all the defined Testcases from all three VITAL-5G facilities in this deliverable. Instead, an exemplary Testcase is provided by each of the facilities, while the rest of the Testcases can be found on the project’s shared working space Teamwork⁴ (access is restricted to project participants). The GR exemplary Testcase can be found in **Annex III: GR facility Service Oriented Testcases Example**, and describes TC02_GR_S.

All the GR facility service-oriented Testcases can be found on Teamwork⁴.

An important part of the defined TCs are also the kind of KPIs that are being recorded/logged during each of the experiments and that will later help with the performance evaluation of the specific services. The Common set of KPIs that was presented in Section 3.2 is constantly being logged and reported via the automatic reporting mechanism, but besides the common KPIs, additional KPIs are needed to be recorded per facility and use case in order to provide the full picture of this service. These KPIs are service and/or application specific and hence only apply to the specific trial facility where this particular experiment is executed.

For the GR facility these “custom” KPIs are mostly related with evaluating the performance of the AGV, and the accuracy of its movements within the warehouse. They are split into two sub-categories, namely *Service level KPIs*, meant to assist with the evaluation of the envisioned T&L services and *Application/AGV level KPIs* meant to assist with the evaluation of the user experience and application performance as well as with the evaluation of the AGV’s various functionalities. Table 19 and Table 20 below present the definition of the GR facility custom

³ Fixed camera placed within the warehouse, providing an overview of the trial location area, where the AGV moves

⁴ <https://inlecom.eu.teamwork.com/#/projects/1825878/files?catid=1824943>

service level and application/AGV level KPIs, respectively. These KPIs are used in the definition of each of the Testcases.

Table 19: Custom service level KPIs used for the GR facility Testcases

KPI ID	KPI name	Explanation	Scenarios
GR_SL_KPI_1	Avg_Order Line_Pick time	Average time duration to complete the picking of an order line. An order is comprised of multiple order lines. The number of order lines per order is variable	a. Without the use of the AGV b. With the use of the AGV
GR_SL_KPI_2	Avg_number_Order lines per hour	Average number of order lines picked per hour	a. Without the use of the AGV b. With the use of the AGV
GR_SL_KPI_3	Avg_MH_for pallet transport_per hour	Average number of Man Hours spent per hour for pallet transport	a. Without the use of the AGV b. With the use of the AGV
GR_SL_KPI_4	Avg_number_Pallets Transported	Average number of pallets transported per hour with the same number of employees	a. Without the use of the AGV b. With the use of the AGV
GR_SL_KPI_5	Avg-number_steps_per hour	Average number of steps per employee per hour for the transportation of boxes/pallets	a. Without the use of the AGV b. With the use of the AGV
GR_SL_KPI_6	Avg_number_steps_per hour_docs	Average number of steps per employee per hour for the transportation of documents	a. Without the use of the AGV b. With the use of the AGV
GR_SL_KPI_7	AGV_distance_covered	Distance covered by the AGV while performing relevant tasks	
GR_SL_KPI_8	AGV_time_operational	Time during which the AGV was operational performing relevant tasks	
GR_SL_KPI_9	Avg_number_Order lines per hour_SIM	Average number of order lines picked per hour after the optimization of the product location based on the recommendations of the Digital Twin / SIM output.	To be compared with the result of GR_SL_KPI_2 under similar circumstances.

Table 20: Custom Application/AGV level KPIs used for the GR facility Testcases

KPI ID	KPI name	Explanation	Scenarios / comments
GR_AL_KPI_1	Avg_Localization_Error	Measure the average deviation of the AGV location from the target location.	Direct the AGV to a known location and measure the deviation. Meant to show the reliability of the AGV movement within the working environment

GR_AL_KPI_2	Avg_Map_Generation_Rate	Measure the rate (meters ² /sec) in which a map of the warehouse can be created.	Direct the AGV to map an area with specific properties. Meant to show the efficiency of the mapping process considered
GR_AL_KPI_3	Avg_Navigation_Speed	Measure the speed in which the AGV can navigate a specific area (e.g. corridor)	Free corridor vs occupied corridor (obstacles every 10-15 meters). Meant to show the navigation speed of the robot inside the facilities based on the environment complexity
GR_AL_KPI_4	Avg_Follow-me_Human-AGV_Distance_Deviation	Measure the average deviation of the distance between location of the AGV and distance configured by the system when the system is in Follow-Me mode	Put the AGV in the follow-me mode and simulate a picking scenario. Meant to show the reliability of the Follow-Me functionality
GR_AL_KPI_5	Avg>Loading_Time	Measure the average time required by the AGV to get below the load and lift a platform until the AGV is ready to move	Direct the AGV to a position near the load carrying platform and direct it to load it. Meant to show how long it takes to complete an important logistics operation
GR_AL_KPI_6	Avg_Unloading_Time	Measure the average time required to unload and escape a load carrying platform.	Direct the AGV to a position and ask to unload it
GR_AL_KPI_7	Avg_E2E_Command_Latency	Measure the average time required for the robot to start an operation when a command is sent	Direct the AGV to perform different commands and measure the time difference in application layer
GR_AL_KPI_8	Dropped_Packets_Ratio	Ratio of dropped packets over total packets transmitted observed from the application layer	
GR_AL_KPI_9	Max_Throughput	Maximum throughput experienced by the AGV and the UE, observed from the application layer	

4.2.1.3 RO facility Testcases

This subsection describes the test cases defined for the 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras (RO) use case. The test cases are organized in two categories: network-oriented test cases and service-oriented test cases.

In the network-oriented category, test cases targeted at measuring the use case KPIs are divided according to the type of data (GNSS, sensor, camera) that is exchanged between the river vessel and the NetApps over the 5G network. These test cases verify whether the use case network requirements are met. An additional test case is targeted at the orchestration operations to measure the NetApp availability and service downtime.

Test cases in the service-oriented category are organized according to each NetApp of the RO use case (VS9, VA2, VA3 and VA6). For most NetApps they were defined by isolating functionalities that require a limited number of other NetApps. In this way the test cases span the successive levels of NetApps integration. A summary of the RO service-oriented test cases and the custom KPIs to be used in the RO trials are provided in Table 21 and Table 22, respectively.

All the RO facility service-oriented Testcases can be found on Teamwork⁴.

Table 21: RO facility service-oriented test cases

TC_ID	TC Title	TC Description/Goal/Focus
TC01_RO_S_VA2	Test the proper functionality of VA2 for accurate electronic navigation maps creation	Test the proper ingestion of sensor data and the processed results. Expected result are correct, on time and with right format VA2 outputs for accurate electronic navigation maps creation: fused data, data analytics, decisions, warnings, notifications, reports This test requires the following NetApps: VS9, VA2
TC02_RO_S_VA6	Test the proper functionality of VA6 for data-enabled assisted navigation	Test the proper ingestion of video streams and sensor data and the application outputs for assisting the safe navigation based on environmental data. Expected result are correct, on time and with right format VA6 output in order to provide assisted navigation for collision avoidance. This test requires the following NetApps: VS9, VA2, VA6
TC03_RO_S_VA3	Test the proper functionality of VA3 for predictive maintenance	Test predictive maintenance and sanity checks applied on the sensor data for ship safety purposes using remote inspection & risk assessment methods. Expected results are analytics, warnings, notifications, reports. This test requires the following NetApps: VS9
TC04_RO_S_VS9	Test the proper functionality of VS9 for data collection	Test the proper ingestion of ship sensors and ship video streams and the application outputs. Expected result are API endpoints towards edge nodes and 5G network and API endpoints towards other NetApps This test requires the following NetApps: VS9
TC05_RO_S_VS9	Detect low depths spots on the Danube waterway and avoid them	Test the functionality of the water depth sensors and their availability to send alert messages, in real time. Expected results are alert messages from the water depth sensors are sent in real time via different communications paths (SMS, email, etc.) This test requires the following NetApps: VS9
TC06_RO_S_VS9	Detect an upcoming obstacle and avoid it	Test the correct detection of obstacles by using YOLO technology applied to video streams. Expected result is that the system can detect an obstacle and send notification to avoid it in time. This test requires the following NetApps: VS9
TC07_RO_S_VS9	Emergency messages dissemination from engine sensor	Test that emergency messages are sent in real time via SMS, email, etc. Expected results are the system is able to send out, in real time, alert messages detected by engine sensors. This test requires the following NetApps: VS9

Table 22: Custom service level KPIs used for the RO facility Testcases

KPI ID	KPI name	Explanation	Scenarios
RO_VS9_KPI_1	Localization accuracy	Difference between positioning timestamps from sensors such as AIS, GPS and depth.	The vessel sends its current position and data from depth sensors to be fused on a map in AIS manner. Timestamps are logged at input and output times.
RO_VA2_KPI_1	Precision of object detection	This measures the accuracy of the video camera recognition algorithm.	Camera and sensor data are recorded to detect dangerous shallow spots. Then the outputs are compared, and precision is calculated.
RO_VA6_KPI_2	Recall of object detection	This measures how well the map contains all obstacles. If the camera often misses obstacles, it will be low.	Camera and sensor data are recorded, and the recall will be calculated.

4.2.2 Network Oriented Testcases

4.2.2.1 Common Testcases

The purpose of these tests is to measure the main 5G network KPIs and validate its performance according to the use case requirements that are identified for each use case, including the NetApps service instantiation, network slice deployment, resource orchestration. The network test consists of measuring and validating the network required KPIs in terms of latency, throughput, network availability and reliability for 5G facilities and services deployment.

The network oriented testcases, described in detail in **Annex V: Common Network Testcases** focus on KPIs such as throughput, latency and packet loss. Additional information can be gathered on jitter, packet delivery ratio, traffic load, coverage area, 5G system bandwidth and slice reliability. Information will be gathered both at slice and network level. Further connectivity IP tests can be performed, and the slice creation time can be assessed.

In order to collect the data, the traffic generated may be reviewed using ICMP/ping, iPerf3 or another testbed specific tool. Then the generators send traffic in order to perform measurements as it is received by the probes. The values are collected in common format for all test beds. KPIs are evaluated and dashboards can be created in order to better review the results, using the real/near-real-time automatically collected or manually collected data.

All three VITAL-5G testbeds will implement these common network oriented testcases or slight variations as will be explained respectively in the following sub-sections, targeting to deliver a thorough evaluation of the performance of the respective 5G networks.

4.2.2.2 BE Network Testcases

In this subsection we provide an overview of the network-oriented test cases defined for the Automated Vessel Transport (BE) use case. In the network-oriented category, test cases targeted at measuring the use case KPIs are divided according to the type of data (GNSS, sensor, camera) that is exchanged between the vessel and the

NetApps over the 5G network. These test cases verify whether the use case network requirements are met. An additional test case is targeted at the orchestration operations to measure the NetApp availability and service downtime. The overview of the BE facility network oriented TCs, are provided in Table 23.

Table 23: Overview of the Network-oriented test cases - Antwerp (BE) facility

TC_ID	TC Description/Goal
TC01_BE_N	Transmitting packets with sensor and GNSS (location, speed, heading) data collections from the vessel to the NetApps on 5G Testbed (VS8), KPIs: E2E latency, jitter, reliability, peak throughput, packet loss, infrastructure KPIs (CPU/memory load). Measuring KPIs for the packets that carry sensor/GNSS data from the vessel to the NetApps (uplink), and for the packets that send predicted voyage plan and assistance recommendation from NetApps to the vessel (downlink)
TC02_BE_N	Transmitting packets with camera stream from the vessel to the NetApps on 5G Testbed (VS6, VA5) KPIs: E2E latency, jitter, reliability, peak throughput, packet loss, infrastructure KPIs (CPU/memory load). Measuring KPIs for the packets that carry camera feed data from the vessel to the NetApps (uplink), and for the packets that send predicted voyage plan and assistance recommendation from NetApps to the vessel (downlink)
TC03_BE_N	Orchestration operations: performing NetApp deployment on the 5G testbed, and measuring the time needed for NFV MANO (OSM) to deploy/scale NetApp on the 5G Testbed, KPIs: platform KPIs (orchestration-related KPIs)

4.2.2.3 GR Network Testcases

The network tests described by the common network-oriented TCs presented in **Annex V** will be executed to evaluate the Athens 5G testbed. Additional network testing for the Athens testbed will be performed and will include connectivity tests for the IPSec tunnel connection with the Romanian testbed and more detailed latency, throughput and jitter testing between the components of the testbed.

The connectivity between the Athens testbed and the NetApp container repository located in the Romanian testbed is established with an IPSec tunnel. The connection will be tested for reliability and performance with the help of tools such as ping.

Detailed tests accompanying the common end to end tests of Section 4.2.2.1, will be performed to analyse the performance of the individual components and connections of the Athens testbed. To this regard, probes will be placed on various network places as mentioned in deliverable D3.1 [6] Sections 3.3.7 & 3.3.8. These probes will help analyse the individual network components and connections in terms of latency, jitter, throughput and packet loss ensuring that the use case KPIs are satisfied. Additionally, the Athens testbed will not utilize a MEC as described in D3.2 Section 3.3.2 due to the low latency reported. To ensure that the low latency requirements are met, probes will be placed between the ends of the transport network and latency measurements will be taken.

4.2.2.4 RO Network Testcases

In this subsection we provide the specific network measurements and test-case KPIs for Orange Romania testbed, results measured in real-time and in relation to the specific NetApps running in the infrastructure, measurements extracted from different probes installed in Romanian testbed, as described in **Annex V**. All the testcases envisioned in Table 24 are based on the standard 3GPP 5G SA KPIs and network related KPIs, methodology described in **Annex V**:

- 5G Network Performance_Bandwidth
- 5G Network Performance_Bandwidth_slice
- 5G_Test_Bed_Manual slice instantiation and termination

- 5G Network Load Performance QoS for slice

Table 24: Overview of the Network-oriented test cases/KPIs- RO facility

Network Domain	TC_ID	TC Description and KPIs
Radio	TC_01_RAN	5G SA traffic volumes
	TC_02_RAN	5G SA Call Setup Success rate
	TC_03_RAN	5G SA Drop Call rate
	TC_04_RAN	Average reported CQI
	TC_05_RAN	Average number of Users
	TC_06_RAN	5G SA average user throughput
	TC_07_RAN	Alarms
	TC_08_RAN	5G MDT (3GPP 37.320) reporting UL/DL user QoS and advanced positioning
Core	TC_01_CN	5G SA Core link utilization
	TC_02_CN	5G SA Core latency
	TC_03_CN	5G SA Core network traffic
	TC_04_CN	5G SA Core subscriber/slice traffic
IP/TX Network	TC_01_TX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IN/OUT octets • IN/OUT errors • IN/OUT discards • IN/OUT unicasts • IN/OUT non-unicasts • IN/OUT utilization
	TC_02_TX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Throughput • lost packets • lost packets percentage • Delay • Delay variation • Jitter
Orchestration	TC_01_OSM	5G NetApps deployment and service slice instantiation for specific NetApp data traffic.

5 User / Trialling Manual

This section provides a guideline for experimenters to prepare and execute experiments in the VITAL-5G system and particularly target third-parties willing to use the VITAL-5G platform to verify the performance of their NetApps and services in a VITAL-5G testbed. A checklist with the steps to design and prepare an experiment are defined in section 5.1, highlighting the collaborative interactions that are needed between experimenters and testbed administrators for the successful definition of experiments able to exploit the specific capabilities of the selected VITAL-5G testbed. Section 5.2 describes the procedures for experiment setup and configuration, starting from the configuration of assets in VITAL-5G platform and target testbed (mostly handled by VITAL-5G personnel on the basis of the indications provided by the experimenter), up to the onboarding of NetApps and service and experiment blueprints on the platform, with their preliminary testing, in charge to the user. Finally, the steps for the trial execution are explained in section 5.3, while section 5.4 provides an overview about how to retrieve the experiment results.

5.1 Trial preparation checklist

The preparation of a VITAL-5G trial needs a careful definition of the planned experiments, interacting actively with the administrator of the VITAL-5G testbed selected to host the trial. This collaboration will allow to quickly verify the feasibility of the various tests, to refine the trial procedures and to produce detailed test case templates (see deliverable D1.4 [3]) to drive the experiments execution and evaluation. Moreover, the testing environment will be prepared and customized on the basis of the trial needs, while the trial components to be provided by the users (e.g., NetApps, test scripts, etc.) will be preliminarily tested in the lab.

The various actions required for the trial definition and preparation, with the involved actors, are reported in Table 25.

Table 25: Checklist for trial preparation

Step	Action	Responsible
Trial definition	High-level description of the planned trial, including for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment descriptor • Expected capabilities from VITAL-5G infrastructure, including target testbed • Brief description of components to be deployed in VITAL-5G testbed, with high-level experiment architecture (e.g., how the components interact each other) • Vertical service KPIs and relationship with network KPIs • Test cases high-level description, e.g., objective, parameters, expected results. 	Experimenter
	Preliminary evaluation and feasibility assessment of the planned trial. This involves an active interaction between experimenter and testbed administrator to clarify open issues and finalize trial scope and high-level design.	Testbed administrator, jointly with the experimenter
	Initial definition of the list of test cases to be executed for the UC trial, based on the test case template defined in D1.4. This action includes the design of the testing environment, which should be validated by the testbed administrator.	Experimenter (In collaboration with the testbed administrator for the final validation and acceptance of the testing environment design)

Testing environment preparation	Experiment scheduling (planned period and duration).	Experimenter and testbed administrator
	Installation, configuration and testing of external hardware brought by the experimenter.	Experimenter, with supervision from the testbed administrator (or technicians)
	Configuration and testing of testbed hardware.	Testbed administrator or technicians
	Configuration of VITAL-5G testbed infrastructure for the given UC/trial. For example, VPNs, firewall and routing rules, tenants, projects and/or quotas in VIM and NFVO, network slices (only if dynamic slice provisioning is not supported), related entries in VITAL-5G multi-site inventory. Verification of UEs connectivity.	Testbed administrator or technicians
	<Optional> Installation and configuration of network probes and tools for custom infrastructure monitoring.	Testbed administrator or technicians
	<Optional> Verification of external connectivity (e.g., to external testbed, public cloud or services in public Internet).	Testbed administrator or technicians
NetApps and Service preparation	Preliminary functional validation of NetApps and service in lab., with manual deployment and configuration.	NetApp Developer
	<Optional> Functional verification of NetApps mechanisms for generation and publishing of NetApp-specific service metrics in VITAL-5G Monitoring Platform.	NetApp Developer **
	<Optional> Preparation and functional verification of scripts for automated testing.	NetApp Developer **
** May need support from VITAL-5G technicians in case of 3 rd party experiments.		

5.2 Trial setup & configuration

The trial setup and configuration is the phase where the system is properly configured and preliminarily verified, so that it is ready for the actual execution of the trial. This phase involves a number of initial actions, related to the configuration of the VITAL-5G system on the basis of the trial specification, that are in charge of VITAL-5G personnel responsible for the configuration of (i) the VITAL-5G Platform and (ii) the testbed selected to host the trial. After this initial configuration, the platform is ready to onboard the NetApps and all the blueprints required to define the service under test and the experiments to run during the trial. The onboarding of the blueprints can be performed entirely through the web GUI of the VITAL-5G Portal. Preliminary manual and functional testing of provisioning procedures and remote access to the NetApps are strongly recommended to guarantee a smooth execution of the trials.

The steps and detailed actions to be performed during the trial setup and configuration, with the involved actors, are reported in Table 26.

Table 26: Actions for trial setup and configuration

Step	Action	Responsible
Configurations of users in VITAL-5G platform and VITAL-5G testbed	Configuration of users and use cases in VITAL-5G platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Configuration of group associated to the use case 	VITAL-5G Platform administrator

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of users’ accounts with related roles and groups • User groups associated with a NetApp-Experiment to have access to the relevant information, by allowing the subscription to specific topics (Common KPIs/ automatic reporting) 	
	Setup of VPNs to allow the users to access the testing environment on the target testbed (i.e., to reach the deployed NetApps). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allowing access to the files referring to custom KPIs/manual reporting. Experimenters to also have access to final MRT files. 	Testbed administrator
NetApps images onboarding	Onboarding of NetApps images in target testbed.	NetApp Developer, with support from testbed administrator
	Functional testing of NetApps in target testbed, including instantiation, execution and termination.	NetApp Developer, with support from testbed administrator
NetApps packages, Service and Experiment blueprints onboarding and preliminary testing (using VITAL-5G Portal)	Onboarding and validation of NetApp blueprints, Vertical Service blueprints, Test Case blueprints and experiment blueprint.	NetApp Developer, Vertical Service Developer, Experimenter **
	Vertical Service provisioning and functional validation of the running service, including testing of NetApps’ access via VPN.	Experimenter **
	Refinement of test cases, based on test case template.	Experimenter
** May need support from VITAL-5G technicians in case of 3 rd party experiments.		

5.3 Trial execution

The trial execution phase is the most challenging phase of the project lifecycle where all the steps described in the trial planning will be implemented, so results will be collected and evaluated. The execution allows, in a secure virtualized 5G environment, to test, validate and verify the T&L NetApps and the network connectivity that might impact the performance of single NetApps or end-to-end T&L service as a whole.

After the trial preparation, set-up and configuration, the VITAL-5G platform is ready to host the experiments of the trials. Based on the oriented testcases defined for each specific trial site (Section 4.2.1) and according to the facility trial planning (Section 4.1), testing/trialing is executed by splitting it in two categories: network-oriented test cases and service-oriented test cases. In the network-oriented category, test cases target use case KPIs, whilst test cases in the service-oriented category are organized according to each NetApp of the use case.

Each service-oriented experiment will require its own list of steps to be executed by the experimenters to create the virtual environment, instantiate the service, connect to and launch the applications’ components, interact with the system from the UEs, collect and analyze the data, etc. Some of these actions can be executed directly by the VITAL-5G Portal and automated using the tools offered by the VITAL-5G platform, other require manual actions from the experimenters. The details of these experiment-specific procedures are documented in the test cases, following the template defined in D1.4 [3]. However, it is possible to recognize a common pattern for the execution of a generic experiment related to a T&L service in the VITAL-5G platform, as follows:

- **Instantiation of the T&L vertical service** related to the experiment in the target VITAL-5G testbed. This action is executed through the VITAL-5G web Portal and it is handled by the Service Lifecycle Manager at the VITAL-5G platform (see D2.1 [4], section 5.2). All the NetApps' components are automatically deployed and interconnected, the network slices are activated and configured, and the monitoring platform is configured to collect the related monitoring data. At this stage, the NetApps VMs or containers are up and running; the experimenter can connect to their console (using the VPN with the VITAL-5G testbed) to inspect logs or perform manual actions on them.
- **Creation of the experiment on top of the instantiated T&L service.** This action is executed through the VITAL-5G web Portal and it is handled by the Experiment Lifecycle Manager at the VITAL-5G platform (see D2.1 [4], section 5.4). At this stage, the T&L service is locked and reserved for the execution of the experiment.
- **Launch of the experiment execution.** This action is executed through the VITAL-5G web Portal and it is handled by the Experiment Lifecycle Manager at the VITAL-5G platform (see D2.1, section 5.4). The experiment is configured, the generation of monitoring data is configured and activated together with the elements responsible to collect and analyze them (e.g., the Results Analytics and the AI-based Performance Diagnostics components, see D2.1 sections 5.5 and 5.6), and the automated testing scripts, if defined in the test case blueprint, are launched. At this stage, the experiment is up and running and the related data are properly collected and labelled in the VITAL-5G platform.
- **Execution of manual actions in the running experiment.** This includes all the actions performed manually during the trial, e.g., users interacting with the T&L service, service administrator modifying some of its configurations, etc. These actions are experiment specific and they are not mediated through the VITAL-5G platform, but they usually involve the interaction with the frontends offered by the NetApps under tests.

For a better alignment, the trial execution phase takes into consideration the various significant milestones and deliverables of the project and the 3rd party experimentation activities (onboarded in Stage 5, Table 15) in each of the trial sites. Information and metrics are automatically collected through the Results Analytics component which produces the specific pilot trials' KPIs (Network oriented, Service oriented, Platform oriented and Infrastructure oriented) centralized in the Monitoring Platform with the support of the measurement reporting templates (see section 5.4 for further details about results collection and analysis).

Finally, the experimenter has the possibility to visualize in the web GUI of the VITAL-5G Portal the results through the monitoring dashboard for a primary evaluation and further refining process. Experimenter can improve, raise blocking issues or dependencies by launching iterations for possible adjustments. The iteration review provides the opportunity to assess progress as well as make any adjustments ahead of the next iteration. Following this refinement process, results are ready for the collection and storage phase.

5.4 Results collection & storage

This section refers to the collection of all the relevant KPIs (prior and during the trials), as well as post-processing analytics/diagnostics collected and stored. Depending on the KPI and analytics/diagnostics needed per service, a series of steps need to be considered.

Common KPIs supported by the VITAL-5G monitoring framework are published on a ZeroMQ bus and can be easily consumed. Once collected they can be further processed through dynamically configurable rules by the Results Analytics component, displayed in custom monitoring dashboards. They can then be accessed via programmable APIs for further analysis, e.g., by the AI-diagnostics component for post-processing or other 3rd parties. Manually reported KPIs in CSV format along with MRTs can be found at the ORO provided facilities hosting the VITAL-5G platform and are also accessible for post-processing. The options for size of storage and duration of persistency can be judged on a service basis. Table 27 provides an overview of the VITAL-5G results collection and storage relevant actions.

Table 27: Actions for results collection and storage

Step	Action	Responsible
Setting storage options (for both automatic and manual reporting)	Configuring options for storage of historical data and duration of persistency is done at a service-level and in coordination with all the parties involved.	Testbed administrator, VITAL-5G Platform administrator, NetApp Developers, Experimenter
Results collection and storage (Common KPIs/ automatic reporting)	<p>During trial, experimenter may subscribe to specific topics based on the selected KPIs to be collected, where necessary.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Where applicable, experimenters may subscribe to processing/ analytics on the collected KPIs by the Result Analytics module. 	Experimenter (based on VITAL-5G Platform capabilities)
	After the trial, extraction of automated reporting for post-processing results coming from the AI-diagnostics component based on collected KPIs and analytics.	Experimenter (based on VITAL-5G Platform capabilities)
Results collection and storage (Custom KPIs/ manual reporting)	Custom KPIs selected in the TCBs are stored in the various target testbeds and then along with MRTs are stored centrally at the ORO testbed from which they are accessible for postprocessing by the experimenter after the trial.	Target & ORO Testbed administrator, NetApp Developers, Experimenter

6 Conclusions

In this document, the end-to-end Trial and Experimentation methodology of the VITAL-5G project was presented, along with the tools and processes that have been created and put into place to support trial planning, monitoring and alignment as well as the experimentation guidelines to properly configure, execute and analyse experiments.

The high-level end-to-end experimentation methodology presented in Section 2, depicts how the different tools and processes fit together to offer an end-to-end framework that will assist experimenters to set-up, configure and execute their experiments, while at the same time it will ensure that all proper actions have been taken to log the necessary metrics that will guide the evaluation process, and to guarantee the traceability and replicability of all the experiments carried out within the VITAL-5G facilities. The experimentation methodology provides information on how the various experiments should be defined in detail, using the Testcase templates, prior to their execution, what are the necessary preparatory steps before executing an experiment, which tools engage in metrics logging and how their outcomes are stored and processed. The proper participation of both internal and external experimenters in the VITAL-5G experiments has also been taken into account by defining the appropriate consent forms that need to be signed by anyone participating in the experiments/trials.

One of the key characteristics of the experimentation methodology of VITAL-5G is the elaborate measurement framework that was designed to serve the needs of the complex VITAL-5G ecosystem, i.e., one central platform providing access and monitoring the experiment in three distinct experimentation facilities. In order for this common framework to be functional, a Common Data Format was defined and agreed among all partners which will facilitate the reporting of the necessary KPIs from the three facilities. In order to ensure the thorough investigation and analysis of both the 5G networks and the T&L services and NetApps, both automatic and manual measurements and reporting have been defined within the VITAL-5G framework. The automatic reporting ensures that all the agreed common KPIs (as reported in Section 3.2) are always logged and reported during experimentation on all three VITAL-5G facilities/testbeds, and also enables the common results analytics & diagnostics services of the platform, while the manual measurements and reporting (again based on commonly agreed metrics (csv format)) may take place in non-real time at each of the facilities and be used to validate and benchmark the performance of the individual 5G SA testbeds.

Besides the automatic and manual measurements and reporting which are based on the commonly agreed KPIs, additional custom metrics/KPIs are logged at each facility in order to enable the performance evaluation of each of the targeted T&L services and respective NetApps. These KPIs are meant to evaluate the specific vertical service offered within each experiment and assess the added value of 5G connectivity for each of them. All the available metrics/KPIs that have been logged during experimentation (automatic & manual, common & custom) are combined and analysed using the Measurement Report Template, in order to offer valuable insights and a holistic view of the performance experienced by the user during each experiment.

One of the most valuable contributions of this deliverable is the detailed definition of all the Testcases to be executed by internal experimenters over the VITAL-5G facilities, targeting the thorough evaluation of the 5G testbeds performance and the T&L services and NetApps. The definition of these TCs will facilitate the proper scheduling and planning of all the experimentation facilities, while they also ensure that there is a clear goal behind every experiment executed over the VITAL-5G facilities. An initial planning regarding the expected dates that experimentation may take place over the VITAL-5G facilities, based on the defined TCs and expected availability of the testbeds has also been provided, taking into account 3rd party experimentation as well.

Finally, a user/trialing manual has been created as part of the WP4 activities, meant to assist both internal and 3rd party experimenters, offering key information about the experimentation methodology adopted by VITAL-5G and guidelines about processes such as experiment preparation, configuration, execution, results collection, and more.

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Annex I: Consent form for trials

Consent form VITAL-5G

You are invited to join the VITAL-5G innovation project to take part in a **survey** related to this project. VITAL-5G is a 36-month EU-funded project with the purpose of innovating the Transport and Logistic sector using the 5G functionalities.

What is the purpose of the **survey**?

With this survey we want to gather your feedback on your experience as experimenter in the VITAL-5G project. We will ask you about your experience to improve the impact of our project on the transport and logistics sector.

What personal information will we collect and why?

During this **survey** we will collect the following personal information from you

- Identification and contact information to manage and conduct these surveys.
- Your professional opinion to improve our research and focus area with regards to the transport and logistics sector

How will we handle your personal information?

The information collected during this **survey** will be used to improve the impact of the VITAL-5G project and will only be accessible for employees of the **<partner performing the workshop/focus group/interview/... >** that need access to perform their tasks. All other stakeholders will only have access to the anonymized information.

The information will be stored on a secure location for 5 years after the end of the project. After this the information will be removed from our systems

What rights do you have with regard to your personal information?

We collect your data on the basis of your consent, which means that you have the right to stop your cooperation at any time without having to give a reason. This can easily be done in writing by e-mail to **<contact information>**, after which we will process your cancellation as soon as possible. In addition, you can request us to obtain a copy of the personal data collected by us and / or to correct or delete this information in our files.

Questions

For all your questions and / or comments about the processing of your personal data, you can contact us via the email address **<contact information>** For further information on the VITAL-5G project, you can consult the project web site at <https://www.vital5g.eu/>.

If you have any concerns, complaints or further questions regarding the VITAL-5G project you can contact the local representative: **<Contact details of the DPO of the responsible partner>** or the project DPO Klaas.ghesquiere@imec.be

Consent

I declare that I have read the information and agree to participate in the **survey** as described in this consent form.

Name participant:

Date:

Signature:

Annex II: BE Facility Service Oriented Testcases Example

The complete set of files that describe test cases is available on the project’s Teamwork space⁵

Table 28: GR Facility example service oriented Testcase TC02_GR_S

Testcase ID	TC01_BE_S_VS6 – Voyage planning
Trial site	Port of Antwerp
Testcase type	Service specific UC1 / Vessel Autonomous Control / VS6 – Autonomous Vessel Navigation
Description	<p>This test will consist in testing the ability of the planning algorithms to generate a trajectory from current position (position A) to goal (position B) without obstacles. The trajectory is defined according to two different settings: 1) Straight line from A to B; 2) B hidden after corner or challenging channel configuration. In this test, the predicted trajectory should be validated by demonstrating that the vessel can actually follow the corresponding points in a realistic way of sailing (minimal deviation to global points) and that it can reach the goal.</p> <p>This testcase will test in an end-to-end manner:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - That the current vessel position, goal position and static (no-obstacle) map are correctly received and taken into account by the algorithm; - That the planning is correctly performed up to the goal.
Test environment and deployment	<p>The diagram illustrates the test environment and deployment architecture. It is divided into three main infrastructure layers: On Site Testbed Infrastructure at UC1 Facilities (Seafar), 5G Infrastructure (Telenet), and UC1 Cloud Infrastructure (imec). The On Site Testbed layer includes a vessel icon and a person icon. The 5G Infrastructure layer includes a 5G RAN tower icon and a 5G Core cloud icon. The UC1 Cloud Infrastructure layer includes server rack icons. The central part of the diagram shows a communication flow: a vessel icon is connected to a Seafar exclusive vessel control box, which is connected to the 5G RAN, then to the 5G Core, and finally to a Vessel Autonomous Control (VS6) box. The VS6 box is connected to a Remote Vessel Monitoring box, which contains four sub-components: VS7, VS8, VA5, and VS5. Below the Remote Vessel Monitoring box is a NetApp Orchestrator box. Arrows indicate the flow of data and control between these components.</p>

⁵ <https://inlecom.eu.teamwork.com/#/projects/1825878/files?catid=1824943>

<p>Cross-referencing</p>	<p>Relevant NetApps</p>	<p>VS5 – Remote Vessel Navigation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApp package: NAB_uc1_vs5_v01 <p>VS8 – On board data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApp package: NAB_uc1_vs8_v01
	<p>Reference Service</p>	<p>Vertical Service: Vessel Autonomous Control</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical Service Blueprint: VSB_uc1_service1_v01
	<p>Reference Experiment</p>	<p>Experiment blueprint: ExpB_uc1_service1_global_tc01_v01</p>
<p>5G Network Environment</p>	<p>5G Network settings / configuration</p>	<p>3GPP 5G SA Rel.16 SA</p> <p>5G SA RAN details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vendor: Ericsson • Software version: 1.2 • Radio Specs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Freq bands, spectrum: 2496 – 2690 Hz ○ Modulation: QPSK ○ mMIMO: 64T64R ○ Interfaces: Xn ○ RAN slice template: SST1 ○ gNB configuration: manual <p>5G SA Core</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core elements: UPF • Core Deployment: IaaS • Core deployment: manual • Core Interfaces/Exposed APIs: N4

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slice deployment: dynamic • Slice templates: SST1 • Slice configuration: dynamic • DNN for configured slices (1/2): SNSSAI • 5G QoS: latency <p>5G Backhaul:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gNB N2/N3 integration: high speed 10Gbps • Transport network configuration: manual • Transport QoS: latency <p>5G Slices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DNN: DNN1 SST1 • NS1: URLLC slice for IoT sensors (20 MHz @ 3.5GHz, TDD, QoS parameters) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 x environmental IoT sensors ○ 1x remote control module ○ Slice parameters: UL/DL-Latency • NS2: eMBB slices for camera feeds (100 MHz @ 3.5 GHz, TDD) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1x UHD camera ○ 2x smartphones ○ Slice parameters: UL/DL-Latency
	<p>Testcase traffic flows</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Server (path planning algorithms) or experimenter laptop on the vessel to Server (path planning algorithms): static map data • Server (data collection) to server (path planning algorithms): vessel information • Server (remote monitoring) to server (path planning algorithms): goal information • Server (remote monitoring) to server (path planning algorithms): planning information
	<p>Network performance & functional requirements and KPIs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UL Bitrate Min 30 Mbps • Latency max 105 ms • Reliability min 99.9% • Availability min 99.9% • Broadband connectivity min 26Mbps
<p>Components and Configuration</p>	<p>IoT/T&L components (e.g., sensors, IoT gateways, AGVs, etc)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General purpose laptop for experimenter access to server (Vessel) • Computing server possibly with ssh access enabled (imec) for path planning algorithms, data collection and remote monitoring
	<p>Networking</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic generator using iperfv3 for DNNs

	components (e.g., traffic generators, network emulators, network probes)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ TCP/UDP traffic load ○ Background traffic load @ 25% and 50% ● Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) Round Trip Time (RTT) ● Distributed Internet Traffic Generator (D-ITG) for stochastic packet generation ● Network port mirroring ● Core Network probes ● Wireshark analysis
	Components of the SUT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Computing server with ssh access enabled (imec) for path planning algorithms
	Application-level Configuration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Static map data and global points should have been cached before the trial ● Predefined static maps should be manually sent via the ZeroMQ connection in place of the dynamic maps normally sent by VA5.
Key Use-case requirements and KPIs	Functional requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Proper navigation when following the suggested (algorithm) waypoints ● Reach the goal position
	Service KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Setting 1: The planned trajectory should be a straight line. ● Setting 2: The deviation (distance) to the global/optimal waypoints should remain within realistic sailing behavior: no sharp heading change; at least 3 meters away from the quay edges.
	Secondary Service KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● None
Test procedure	Test location / route	The test takes place along the red part of the trajectory in the figure, in a channel next to the Schelde river:

	<p>Pre-conditions</p>	<p>NetApps are deployed in the UC1 cloud, and have been provisioned.</p> <p>5G network has allocated the corresponding slices to the tested VS6 traffic.</p>
	<p>Testcase steps</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The vessel is placed at the entrance of the channel. 2) The servers are configured to received and store the data. 3) The vessel starts to navigate along the channel and data is sent from the vessel (GPS). The server for data collection sends current vessel parameters to the server running the planner, and static map data is sent to the server running the planner either by the same server or by the experimenter (no digital twin involved). The server for monitoring sends captain input (goal) to the server running the planner. The server running the planner sends path suggestions to the server for monitoring. The process iterates until route end or planning failure. Planning data is recorded. 4) The vessel arrives to the goal or planning failures occur. 5) The data is processed and KPIs are evaluated.
<p>Measurements</p>	<p>Methodology</p>	<p>Logging format (to be started at point A):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning data is logged in JSON format upon reception <p>Logged values</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planned vessel positions, actual vessel positions, global waypoints, goal positions

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning failures (number of failures and corresponding vessel positions). <p>Number/duration of test</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting 1: 5 tests will be performed for confidence. In case one of the tests presents outliers, further analysis will be carried out to check the causes. Each test should last around 10 minutes with 10 minutes before each run to configure/stop/rerun the algorithms. The total duration should be around 1 h 40 min, depending on the speed of the vessel. • Setting 2: 4 tests will be performed for confidence. In case one of the tests presents outliers, further analysis will be carried out to check the causes. Each test should last around 20 minutes with 10 minutes before each run to configure/stop/rerun the algorithms. The total duration should be around 2 h, depending on the speed of the vessel.
	Measurement Points	Server running planners and on server for monitoring.
	Calculation process	N/A (visual assessment of planned trajectories)
Expected Result	With the conclusion of this testcase there should be a clear understanding of the performance of the planners in the simplest possible scenario (straight line, no obstacles) and in more challenging situations (corners, turns, narrowing). The goal is to qualitatively assess the discrepancies between planned vessel positions and actual (realistic) positions, and to understand possible planning failures.	

Annex III: GR Facility Service Oriented Testcases Example

The complete set of files that describe test cases is available on the project’s Teamwork space⁶

Table 29: GR Facility example service oriented Testcase TC02_GR_S

TC02_GR_S	AGV based autonomous pallet transfer: From inbound dock to designated storage location	
Trial site	GR (Athens)	
Test case type	<i>Service specific</i> : Autonomous pallet transport	
Description	For the AGV to successfully read the barcode on the pallet, to interact with WMS to identify the proper location, to navigate to the proper location avoiding obstacles, to identify empty spot in targeted location and to successfully deposit the pallet.	
Test environment and deployment	<p>The diagram illustrates the system architecture. On the left, an AGV (Autonomous Guided Vehicle) and a Sensor Pack are shown. The AGV contains a Motion Planner, Messaging Controller, Behavior controller, and Video feed controller. The Sensor Pack contains a Messaging Controller, Sensor Acquisition, and Video feed controller. Both are connected via 5G radio connections to a 5G Access Network. This network connects to a 5G Core Network. The 5G Core Network is linked to a NetApp Atomic Component (MQTT/HTTP gateway) and a Core IoT Controller. The MQTT/HTTP gateway connects to a Persistence service and a Reasoning engine, which are part of the VA1 NetApp. The Core IoT Controller connects to a Logistics LCM and a Planning component, which are part of the VS1 NetApp. A legend defines symbols for NetApp Atomic Components, Internal Connectivity Services, and various endpoints (Internal only, External, External with 5G mobile access) and HW Dependencies.</p>	
Cross-referencing	Relevant NetApps	VA1 Distributed sensor data ingestion fusion & automation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> NetApp package: SensorIngestionAndAutomation (NAB_uc3_va1_v01) VS1 Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> NetApp package: AutonomousNavigation (NAB_uc3_vs1_v01)
	Reference Service	Autonomous pallet transport <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vertical Service Blueprint: VSB_uc3_service1_v01
	Reference Experiment	From inbound dock to designated storage location <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment Blueprint: ExpB_uc3_service1_TC02_GR_S_v01
5G Network Environment	5G Network settings / configuration	3GPP 5G SA Rel.16 SA 5G SA RAN details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vendor: Ericsson Software version: TBD Radio Specs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Freq bands, spectrum: Modulation: mMIMO:

⁶ <https://inlecom.eu.teamwork.com/#/projects/1825878/files?catid=1824943>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Interfaces: Xn ○ RAN slice template: SST1 ○ gNB configuration: manual <p>5G SA Core</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Core elements: AMF, SMF, UPF, AUSF, NRF, UDM, UDR, PCF, NSSF, BSF ● Core Deployment: IaaS ● Core deployment: manual ● Core Interfaces/Exposed APIs: TBD ● Slice deployment: static ● Slice templates: TBD ● Slice configuration: static ● DNN for configured slices (1/2): TBD ● 5G QoS: TBD <p>5G Backhaul:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● gNB N2/N3 integration: high speed 10Gbps ● Transport network configuration: manual ● Transport QoS: latency <p>5G Slices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DNN: DNN1 SST1 ● NS1: URLLC slice for IoT sensors (20 MHz @ 3.5GHz, TDD, QoS parameters) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1x AGV ● NS2: eMBB slices for camera feeds (100 MHz @ 3.5 GHz, TDD) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Environmental sensor pack (incl. Camera) ○ 2x UE
	<p>Test Case traffic flows</p>	<p>Indicate all the traffic flows included in this UC, including their flow direction (DL/UL), e.g.,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● TF1: AGV On board camera to server/platform (UL) ● TF2: AGV to server/platform (UL) ● TF3: UE to server/platform (UL) ● TF4: Sensor Pack to server/platform (UL) ● TF5: Steady Cam to server/platform (UL) ● TF6: server/platform to AGV (DL) ● TF7: server/platform to UE incl. video player(DL)
	<p>Network performance, functional requirements & KPIs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For traffic flow TF1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UL Bitrate Min 20 Mbps ● Latency max 100 ms ● Reliability min 99.99% ● For traffic flow TF2: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UL Bitrate Min 10 Mbps ● Latency max 20 ms ● Reliability min 99.999% ● For traffic flow TF3: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UL Bitrate Min 10 Mbps ● Latency max 100 ms

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliability min 99.99% • For traffic flow TF4: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UL Bitrate Min 10 Mbps • Latency max 100 ms • Reliability min 99.99% • For traffic flow TF5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UL Bitrate Min 20 Mbps • Latency max 100 ms • Reliability min 99.99% • For traffic flow TF6: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DL Bitrate Min 10 Mbps • Latency max 20 ms • Reliability min 99.999% • For traffic flow TF7: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DL Bitrate Min 20 Mbps • Latency max 100 ms • Reliability min 99.99%
<p>Components and Configuration</p>	<p>IoT/T&L components (e.g. sensors, IoT gateways, AGVs, etc)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AGV <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 5G modem ○ Front Laser Scanner ○ Back Laser Scanner ○ RGBD camera ○ Inertial Measurement Unit ○ Motor encoders • Sensor-pack (incl. camera) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 5G modem ○ USB camera ○ Temperature/Humidity sensor ○ Luminosity sensor ○ Piezo-Vibration sensor • Platform/server <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MQTT broker ○ IoT controller • 5G enabled UE (smartphone/tablet)
	<p>Networking components (e.g. traffic generators, network emulators, network probes)</p>	<p>N/A</p>
	<p>Components of the SUT</p>	<p>Cooperation of the AGV with the VA1 and VS1 NetApps for executing the autonomous pallet transfer scenarios. Especially paying attention to localization accuracy of AGV and obstacle avoidance, proper loading and unloading of the pallets, etc.</p>
	<p>Application level Configuration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AGV Settings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Map resolution (indicative value: 0.05) ○ Costmaps size

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ minimum and maximum linear velocities (indicative values: 0.5 m/s and 1.5 m/s) ○ Visual servoing tolerance parameters (angle and position) ○ Visual servoing approach distance ○ Goal tolerance parameters (angle and position) ● AGV coms with NetApp settings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Camera resolution (indicative value: 720x480) ● Sensor pack coms with NetApp settings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sensors sampling rates ○ Camera resolution (indicative value: 720x480)
<p>Key Use-case requirements and KPIs</p>	<p>Functional requirements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Correct identification of proper pallet ● Smooth loading of the pallet ● Smooth pallet transport to correct destination without collisions ● Smooth unloading of the pallet in the target area with small unloading deviation ● Successful return to designated default location
	<p>Service KPIs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Service level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ GR_SL_KPI_3: Avg_MH_for pallet transport_per hour ○ GR_SL_KPI_4: Avg_number_Pallets Transported ○ GR_SL_KPI_7: AGV_distance_covered (compared to minimum Manhattan distance) ○ GR_SL_KPI_8: AGV_time_operational (removing idle time from operational time) ● Application level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ GR_AL_KPI_1: Avg_Localization_Error ○ GR_AL_KPI_3: Avg_Navigation_Speed ○ GR_AL_KPI_5: Avg_Loading_Time ○ GR_AL_KPI_6: Avg_Unloading_Time ○ GR_AL_KPI_7: Avg_E2E_Command_Latency ○ GR_AL_KPI_8: Dropped_Packets_Ratio ○ GR_AL_KPI_9: Max_Throughput
	<p>Secondary Service KPIs</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Test procedure</p>	<p>Test location / route</p>	<p>This testcase will take place within the DIA warehouse. The starting point of the AGV will be point A in the below figure at the inbound/outbound docks where pallets are unloaded from trucks. At that point the AGV will load the designated pallet and will autonomously transport it to the finish point (point B in the figure). Different finish points (points B) will be tested throughout the iterations of this testcase to cover most of the warehouse demo area and to investigate potential performance differences based on 5G coverage.</p>

	<p>Pre-conditions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AGV is operational and battery is not empty • User has access rights to issue command • Pallets are loaded onto their trolleys & accessible • Pallets are equipped with the proper paper Tag/marker • Targeted unloading space is not occupied • Tight synchronization of the AGV and server
	<p>Test Case steps</p>	<p>The detailed steps to execute this testcase are presented in Table 30. To more thoroughly test the performance of the AGV/platform for this testcase, 4 different sub-scenarios are envisioned:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scenario 1a: Load any (the first) pallet: The AGV will go to the inbound/outbound docks area once it receives the order for the autonomous pallet transfer, and it will select the first available pallet in its path to be transported. The AGV will scan the barcode on the pallet in order to identify the correct storing location for this pallet. • Scenario 1b: Load specific pallet: The experimenter will instruct the AGV to transport a specific pallet (which is not the first in its way). The AGV will start approaching all the pallets in the inbound/outbound area and scan them until it finds the specific pallet. Once the correct pallet is found, the AGV will load it and will proceed with its transport.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Scenario 2a: clean route to destination:</u> Several end points will be tested for the AGV to transport the pallet. In this scenario the route of the AGV from its starting point (A) to its end point (B) will always be clear of obstacles. • <u>Scenario 2b: obstacle (empty pallet) on the path to destination:</u> In this scenario, the route of the AGV from its start point (A) to any of the possible end points (B) will be obstructed by an obstacle (empty pallets will be used as obstacles).
<p>Measurements</p>	<p>Methodology</p>	<p>There is no fixed measuring frequency for all components. The measurements will be logged as soon as they arrive.</p> <p>The following will be logged for AGV:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timestamp (for synchronization) • Process/Experiment state • Hardware diagnostics • Existence of obstacles • Position <p>The following will be logged for Sensor pack:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timestamp • Hardware diagnostics • Single sensor values e.g. temperature, humidity, luminosity, vibration <p>The following will be logged for the server/platform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timestamp (for synchronization) • Process/Experiment state • Every sensor value sent by AGV or Sensor Pack
	<p>Measurement Points</p>	<p>Application level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AGV • Sensor pack • Server/platform <p>Network level</p> <p>Network probes and software collection tools will be used and installed in different network part, as per facilities availability, to collect the network measurements, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radio to BBU: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> probe 1 will be installed in the end device site and probe 2 will be installed in BBU • Radio to the end of POTP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> probe 1 will be installed in the end device site and probe 3 will be installed before packet core • Radio to the end of packet core <ul style="list-style-type: none"> probe 1 will be installed in the end device site and probe 4 will be installed after packet core

	<p>Calculation process</p>	<p>From all the logs mentioned above, the timestamp and the value of each measurement is processed to estimate composite KPIs such as latency, total distance covered, idle time.</p>
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>With the conclusion of this testcase there should be a clear understanding of the performance of the AGV in autonomous transport mode under different settings and circumstances. The above-mentioned service level and network level KPIs will provide an understanding of how much effort, distance and capital can be saved by using an AGV for day-to-day transport operations, how quickly the AGV can complete this task under varying circumstances, what is the performance of the various functions of the AGV and are they sufficient (indoor localization accuracy, barcode/QR code recognition success rate, accident avoidance, visual recognition of obstacles, etc.) and what is the necessary network performance (latency, throughput, reliability, etc.) in order to accommodate this service.</p>	

Table 30: Detailed steps of Testcase TCo2_GR_S

<p>Use Case ID:</p>	<p>WC_WA_1</p>
<p>Use Case Name:</p>	<p>Autonomous pallet transfer to designated storage area via AGV</p>
<p>Description:</p>	<p>Instructing the AGV to pick-up a certain pallet from location (X1, Y1), determine its correct storage location (X2, Y2), and autonomously transferring the pallet to that location.</p>
<p>Trigger:</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User Command 2. Part of storage sequence program (i.e., transfer all pallets in the inbound dock area to their respective storage locations)
<p>Preconditions:</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user must be logged in to the server/platform 2. The user must have the correct privileges to issue this command 3. The user must possess a UE connected to the server/platform, to issue the command
<p>Post conditions:</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The pallet is positioned in the designated location right in front of its storage location 2. The pallet is in the exact same condition as when it was picked-up 3. No accidents have occurred with other AGVs or humans
<p>Normal Flow:</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user uses their UE to navigate to the section of “Autonomous Pallet Transfer” of the mobile application 2. The user selects among two options displayed at the GUI of the mobile APP: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Single pallet transfer → transfer a specific pallet, uniquely identified, to its designated location. In this case, filling in either field 3.c or 3.d, becomes mandatory. b. Bulk transfer → transfer all pallets from the designated pick-up area to their respective delivery/storage areas, one after the other. In this case only field 3.a is mandatory. 3. The user inserts the relevant information for the pallet to be transferred and sends the command to the AGV when finished (presses the designated button to start the process). The provided information are: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Pick-up location coordinates (X1, Y1) [Mandatory] b. Delivery location coordinates (X2, Y2) [Optional] c. Pallet ID [Optional] d. Pallet cargo owner (CRG_OWN) [Optional]

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> e. Scheduled time of transfer [Optional] 4. The server/platform receives the command and checks if the “Scheduled time of transfer” field has been filled in: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. If no, then the command is to be executed immediately and proceeds to the next steps b. If yes, the server/platform schedules this task and proceeds to the next steps in the designated date/time. 5. The WCP checks for available AGVs <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. If an AGV is readily available, then the system proceeds to the next step b. If all AGVs are occupied, the command enters a queue to be executed as soon as an AGV becomes available. In this case an Estimated time of execution should be provided to the user via the mobile app 6. The WCP instructs the AGV to move to the designated pick-up location. 7. The AGV approaches the pallet(s) and reads the information from the tag/barcode to uniquely identify the pallet. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Unique identification may happen via the on-board camera (OB_CAM) with the use of a barcode b. Unique identification may happen via the on-board RFID scanner (SCAN) if available, with the use of an RFID tag 8. The AGV transmits the pallet ID to the server/platform. In turn the WCP interacts with the WMS to retrieve the information of the uniquely identified pallet. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. The delivery/storage location and the CRG_OWN is the minimum set of information that should be retrieved. 9. In case the user has provided a pallet ID and/or CRG_OWN in step 3, the WCP cross-references the information retrieved from the WMS with the information provided by the user. The following applies: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. In case the pallet ID and/or the CRG_OWN are a match, the pallet is selected for transfer b. In case none of the two are a match, then the pallet is not selected and the WCP instructs the AGV to move on and scan the next pallet. The process repeats from step 7. c. In case the ID and CRG_OWN fields have not been provided by the user, it is assumed that any pallet from that pick-up point will do, and the pallet is selected for transfer. 10. The AGV moves under the selected pallet, lifts it, and proceeds to transfer it to the designated delivery/storage location. 11. The AGV uses its on-board navigation capabilities to autonomously navigate to the designated delivery/storage location and to avoid any accidents/collisions with other AGVs and/or humans <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Additional information may be offered to the AGV, originating from a steady CAM and sensors and/or UEs, via the server/platform, to assist it with its navigation and/or improvement of its map 12. During the process, the AGV transmits real-time data from its on-board sensors and camera to the WCP, which in turn displays the following information to the user via the mobile App on their UE: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Live feed from the OB_CAM b. Pallet info (ID, CRG_OWN, delivery coordinates) c. Task info (elapsed time, distance covered, Estimated Time of Completion) d. AGV info (current speed, location on the map, battery level) 13. The AGV arrives at the designated delivery/storage location and sets the pallet down. 14. The WCP displays a “Task completed” message to the GUI of the mobile App 15. The WCP stores all relevant data and logs from this Task to a designated data base/internal storage/cloud server to allow for post-processing and extraction of relevant performance statistics 16. The AGV autonomously returns to its designated charging/resting station, or resumes the operation by returning to the designated pick-up location, to pick-up the next pallet, in case “bulk transfer” has been selected by the user in step 2.
Alternative Flow:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Alt. Step 3</u>: The pick-up and delivery locations may also be designated by selecting a point (dropping a pin) to the desired point of the warehouse space through an interactive map displayed to the user. • <u>Alt. Step 8</u>: In case a WMS does not exist or a full integration of the server/platform and the WMS has not been achieved, the relevant pallet information (ID, delivery/storage location and

	<p>CRG_OWN) can be retrieved from a file or entries in a data base that are accessible to the server/platform.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Alt. Step 16:</i> A default location may be set by the user for the AGV to return upon the completion of every task, which may differ than the one mentioned in step 16. Additionally, the AGV may be requested to continuously perform pallet transfers form a specific pick-up area until all pallets have been transferred to their designated locations. In this case, the AGV, upon the completion of a pallet transfer would proceed to return to the originally designated pick-up point, to transfer the next pallet.
Exceptions:	
Business Rules:	
Assumptions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All pallets have Barcode and/or RFID tags in a place visible/accessible to the AGV cameras and scanners • All pallets are placed on top of specialized carriages, allowing the AGV to move below them and lift them for transport

Annex IV: RO facility Service Oriented Testcases Example

The complete set of files that describe test cases is available on the project’s Teamwork space⁷

Table 31: RO Facility example service oriented Testcase TC01_RO_S_VA2

Testcase ID	TC01_RO_S_VA2	
Trial site	Port of Galati	
Testcase type	Service specific UC2 /Accurate electronic navigation maps creation / VA2 - Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing	
Description	<p>Purpose: Test the proper ingestion of sensor data and the processed results Expected result: Correct, on time and with right format VA2 outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fused data • data analytics • decisions • warnings • notifications • reports <p>This test will consist of testing the sensor and video feed performance received from the vessel while navigating through shipyard docks in the Port of Galati. The video feed and data coming from different sensors (GPS, humidity, smoke, velocity, etc.) are transmitted to the navigation centre using wireless protocols over a private 5G network and permit the extension of the Internet connectivity of the sensing system to be used by specific applications, e.g. assisted navigation for avoiding collisions, diagnosis, etc.</p> <p>This Testcase will run in an end-to-end manner and verify that the video generated in the on-board cameras is received in the remote monitoring dashboard of VA2 with the required quality. We will generate first testing data to accurately measure the QoS parameters and network KPIs. Secondly, we will directly use feed from the cameras and analyse the QoE perceived at the monitoring dashboard.</p>	
Test environment and deployment	<p>The diagram, titled 'Testcase Architecture', illustrates the data processing pipeline. It starts with 'Testbed data/ KPIs' and 'External data' entering a 'Data Collection' block. This feeds into 'Data Fusion', which then connects to 'Data Persistence'. From 'Data Persistence', data flows to 'Unsupervised Modelling' and 'Supervised Modelling' blocks, which are part of an 'ML module'. An 'Autotune Engine' and 'ML Registry' are also shown, with bidirectional connections to the ML module. 'External endpoints' provide input to the 'Data Collection' block. Finally, data from 'Data Persistence' is directed 'Towards dashboard & other components/Apps'.</p>	
Cross-referencing	Relevant NetApps	VA2 – Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApp package: NAB_uc2_va2_v01 VA6 – Data Stream Organization

⁷ <https://inlecom.eu.teamwork.com/#/projects/1825878/files?catid=1824943>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApp package: NAB_uc2_va6_v01 <p>VS9 – On board data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApp package: NAB_uc2_vs9_v01 <p>VA3 – Remote inspection & risk assessment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NetApp package: NAB_uc2_va3_v01
	Reference Service	<p>Vertical Service: Accurate electronic navigation maps creation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical Service Blueprint: VSB_uc2_service2_v01
	Reference Experiment	<p>Experiment blueprint: ExpB_uc2_service2_global_tc01_v01</p>
5G Network Environment	5G Network settings / configuration	<p>3GPP 5G SA Rel.16 SA</p> <p>5G SA RAN details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vendor: Ericsson • Software version: 1.2 • Radio Specs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Freq bands, spectrum: 2496 – 2690 Hz ○ Modulation: QPSK ○ mMIMO: 64T64R ○ Interfaces: Xn ○ RAN slice template: SST1 ○ gNB configuration: manual <p>5G SA Core</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core elements: UPF • Core Deployment: IaaS • Core deployment: manual • Core Interfaces/Exposed APIs: N4 • Slice deployment: dynamic • Slice templates: SST1 • Slice configuration: dynamic • DNN for configured slices (1/2): SNSSAI • 5G QoS: latency <p>5G Backhaul:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gNB N2/N3 integration: high speed 10Gbps • Transport network configuration: manual • Transport QoS: latency <p>5G Slices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DNN: DNN1 SST1 • NS1: URLLC slice for IoT sensors (20 MHz @ 3.5GHz, TDD, QoS parameters) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 x environmental IoT sensors ○ 1x remote control module ○ Slice parameters: UL/DL-Latency • NS2: eMBB slices for camera feeds (100 MHz @ 3.5 GHz, TDD) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1x UHD camera ○ 2x smartphones ○ Slice parameters: UL/DL-Latency
	Testcase traffic flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TF1: Probe testing flows to QoS measurements server (UL) on NS2 • TF2: On board camera to video feed dashboard server (UL) on NS2
	Network performance &	<p>Both flows have to perform equally from the 5G network perspective.</p>

	<p>functional requirements and KPIs</p>	<p>For traffic flow TF1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UL Bitrate Min 30 Mbps • Latency max 40 ms • Reliability min 99.980% <p>For traffic flow TF2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UL Bitrate Min 30 Mbps • Latency max 40 ms • Reliability min 99.980%
<p>Components and Configuration</p>	<p>IoT/T&L components (e.g., sensors, IoT gateways, AGVs, etc)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD IP Camera (Vessel) • AIS transponder (Vessel) • Depth sensor (Vessel) • Testing prove device, e.g., general purpose laptop with Ubuntu 18.04 (Vessel) • QoS measurements server, e.g., Ubuntu 18.04 (BEIA cloud) • Video feed dashboard server, e.g., Ubuntu 18.04 (BEIA cloud)
	<p>Networking components (e.g., traffic generators, network emulators, network probes)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic generator using iperfv3 for DNNs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ TCP/UDP traffic load ○ Background traffic load @ 25% and 50% ○ • Real time streaming protocol (RTSP) for video feed • Distributed Internet Traffic Generator (D-ITG) for stochastic packet generation • Network port mirroring • Core Network probes • Wireshark analysis
	<p>Components of the SUT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video feed used in VA2 generated in cameras onboarded in the vessel and received in the Monitoring Dashboard Server
	<p>Application-level Configuration</p>	<p>TF1: traffic generated with time stamps, and counters in the payload to measure one-way delay and packet loss:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UDP traffic, 50Mbps, periodic, packet size constant [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min • TCP traffic, 50Mbps, periodic, packet size constant [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min • UDP traffic, 50Mbps, poisson, packet size constant [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min • TCP traffic, 50Mbps, poisson, packet size constant [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min • UDP traffic, 50Mbps, poisson, packet size poisson [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min • TCP traffic, 50Mbps, poisson, packet size poisson [129,300,1000,1500], duration 1 min <p>TF2: traffic generated directly with the IP camera onboarded in the vessel:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • medium HD quality, H.264, RSTP • Full HD quality, H.264, RSTP • medium HD quality, mp4, WebRTC • Full HD quality, mp4, WebRTC <p>Both configurations will be tested under background traffic load at 0%, 25% and 50% in the 5G network.</p>

Key Use-case requirements and KPIs	Functional requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proper reception of the video feed in the Monitoring Dashboard server for e.g., detection of an obstacle in the vessel’s path, or correct reception and implementation of remote navigation commands
	Service KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Max latency for testing feed (TF1) received in the QoS monitoring server < 20 ms Min bandwidth for testing feed (TF1) received in the QoS monitoring server > 20Mbps Min reliability for testing feed (TF1) received in the QoS monitoring server > 99.99 % Min fps received for video feed (TF2) in the Monitoring Dashboard server > 25fps Min Mean opinion score (MOS) perceived for video feed (TF2) in the Monitoring Dashboard server > Good (4)
	Secondary Service KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None
Test procedure	Test location / route	
	Pre-conditions	<p>NetApps are deployed in the UC2 cloud, and have been provisioned. Vessel is equipped with at least one HD IP Camera, with an AIS transponder that receives the data of the surrounding vessels and at the same time transmit the data of their own vessel and depth sensors. 5G network has allocated the corresponding slices to the tested VA2 traffic (TF1 and TF2).</p>
	Testcase steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The vessel is placed at the entrance of the channel. The servers are configured to received and store the data (TF1 or TF2). The vessel starts to navigate along the channel and while data is sent from the vessel. For TF1, the testing probe device will launch the traffic generator client (iperf3 or D-ITG) with the specific configuration under testing. For TF2, the HD IP Camera will start to send the video feed with the specific configuration under testing. The vessel arrives at the dock. The data is processed and KPIs are evaluated.

		<p>This 5-step procedure will be repeated for all configurations detailed in Application-level Configuration.</p>
<p>Measurements</p>	<p>Methodology</p>	<p>The process of data preparation is based on the following operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • selection of relevant data: selection of attributes (filtering and packaging methods), elimination of anomalies or elimination of duplicate records. • data reduction: sampling or selection of courts. <p>Data preparation generates quality data, which leads to quality patterns. For example, it is possible to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • recover incomplete data, which means that we will no longer have missing values, or that ambiguity will be reduced. • purify the data, which consists of a process of correcting errors or eliminating outliers (unusual or exceptional values). • resolve data inconsistencies, using field knowledge or an expert's decision to resolve existing discrepancies. <p>Logging format (to be started at point A):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Testing prove traffic TF1 is logged in CSV format upon reception. • Vessel video feed logging will be stored in video files for further QoE evaluation. <p>Logged values</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elapsed time • Instantaneous throughput (Mbps), measured at both the 5G RAN and the servers' interfaces <p>Number/duration of test</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10-15 tests will be performed for statistical confidence and their values will be averaged. In case one of the tests presents outliers, further analysis will be carried out to check the causes. Each test should last around 1 minutes. The total duration should be around 10-15 minutes, depending on the speed of the vessel. <p>Synthetic/Background traffic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scenarios with 0%, 25% and 50% background traffic at eMBB slice will be executed.
	<p>Measurement Points</p>	<p>For traffic flow TF1, measurement points at Testing probe device, UE, N3 on core UPF and N6 on server side, and on the QoS Monitoring server.</p> <p>For traffic flow TF2, measurement points at HD IP Camera, UE, N3 on core UPF, N6 on server side and on the Monitoring Dashboard server.</p> <p>From OBU to gNB: Radio Interface</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gNB • UE1 & UE2 • OBU

	<p>Calculation process</p>	<p>Values from multiple test runs will be processed to deliver the final measurements. The delivered values for all mentioned KPIs will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average • Max • Min • 10th percentile • 90th percentile <p>Throughput measurement from the 2 flows (TF1 and TF2) will be averaged to provide an average value for the eMBB channel.</p> <p>For QoE experience perceived in the Monitoring Dashboard server, the following formula will be calculated to obtain the MOS:</p> $MOS = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N R_n}{N}$ <p>Where R are the individual ratings for a given stimulus by N subjects.</p>
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>The results obtained in this testcase are useful to better understand the 5G technology used in combination with the IoT data and the analysis of the provided data is useful in obtaining better results related to the vessels monitoring use case. The data from the IoT sensors and cameras installed on the vessels is used to demonstrate the utility of the 5G network and of the developed applications used in the VITAL-5G project.</p>	

Annex V: Common Network Testcases

Table 32: Network oriented TC addressing 5G bandwidth performance

Testcase ID	Test_ID_01	
Trial site	<Trial site ID>	
Testcase type	5G Network Performance_Bandwidth	
Description	<p>The purpose of this network test is to measure 5G network performance KPIs and validate its performance according to the use case requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Throughput (UL/DL) • E2E Network Latency • Packet Loss <p>The monitoring probes, as presented in the Test environment, are relevant at the 5GRAN Level, 5G Transport level, 5G CN, virtualized Infrastructure and External test application. Series of traffic generators/traffic collectors are implemented/deployed in the testbed, empowering the traffic generation and traffic collection and measurements in different 5G Network points.</p>	
Test environment and deployment	<p style="text-align: center;">Testcase measurement architecture</p>	
Cross-referencing	Relevant NetApps	N/A 5G Network performance
	Reference Service	N/A
	Reference Experiment	N/A
5G Network Environment	5G Network settings / configuration	3GPP 5G SA Rel.16 SA 5G SA RAN details: 5G SA Core: 5G IP/Backhaul:
	Testcase traffic flows	<p>The testcase traffic flow are defined between different 5G testbed Traffic_Generator_Receiver points (TGR_1; TGR_2; TGR_3; TGR_4) measured at different network Probe points (P_1; P_2; P_3; P_4), traffic generator and probes as testbed’s availability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DL traffic flow <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MIN/MAX

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UL traffic flow <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MIN/MAX • Latency measurements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ RTT/ms • Packet loss <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ % packet loss • Jitter <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Deviation ms • Packet Delivery Ratio • Coverage area • 5G System Bandwidth • Slice Reliability 																								
	<p>Network performance & functional requirements and KPIs</p>	<p>The measured KPIs are compared against the D1.1 network KPIs</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="704 674 1369 942"> <thead> <tr> <th>KPI</th> <th>Port of Antwerp</th> <th>Galati Port</th> <th>Athens logistics hub</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Latency (max)</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>DL Throughput (min)</td> <td>30</td> <td>20</td> <td>30</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UL Throughput (min)</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Packet Loss</td> <td>%</td> <td>%</td> <td>%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Jitter</td> <td>Ms</td> <td>Ms</td> <td>ms</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>KPIs measurements results analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation results 	KPI	Port of Antwerp	Galati Port	Athens logistics hub	Latency (max)	20	20	20	DL Throughput (min)	30	20	30	UL Throughput (min)	20	20	20	Packet Loss	%	%	%	Jitter	Ms	Ms	ms
KPI	Port of Antwerp	Galati Port	Athens logistics hub																							
Latency (max)	20	20	20																							
DL Throughput (min)	30	20	30																							
UL Throughput (min)	20	20	20																							
Packet Loss	%	%	%																							
Jitter	Ms	Ms	ms																							
<p>Components and Configuration</p>	<p>IoT/T&L components (e.g., sensors, IoT gateways, AGVs, etc)</p>	<p>N/A for network performance tests</p>																								
	<p>Networking components (e.g., traffic generators, network emulators, network probes)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic generator using iperfv3 • ICMP tool • Network probes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Testbed specific tool • Monitoring software tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Testbed specific tool 																								
	<p>Components of the SUT</p>	<p>N/A</p>																								
	<p>Application-level Configuration</p>	<p>N/A</p>																								
<p>Key Use-case requirements and KPIs</p>	<p>Functional requirements</p>	<p>N/A</p>																								
	<p>Service KPIs</p>	<p>N/A (only network KPIs will be measured)</p>																								
	<p>Secondary Service KPIs</p>	<p>N/A</p>																								

Test procedure	Test location / route	The test is performed at the different network entry points; see Probes_Traffic_Generator test case diagram.
	Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5G network integration completed • Probes/Generators installed • Monitoring software tools installed.
	Testcase steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic is generated through the network (use of ICMP/ping and iPerf) • Generators/Probes/Monitoring tool send/receive traffic and perform measurements • KPIs tables are completed (CSV format) • KPIs are evaluated • Final results analysis
Measurements	Methodology	<p>E2E latency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Network basic KPIs description <p>Throughput</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Network basic KPIs description <p>Packet Loss</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Network basic KPIs description <p>Jitter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Network basic KPIs description <p>Reliability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Network basic KPIs description
	Measurement Points	Network traffic generators, probes and software collection tools are used in the 5G testbeds in different points, see figure.
	Calculation process	<p>Values to be measured and computed (CSV format):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latency (Average) in ms • Latency (Max) in ms • Latency (Min) in ms • Throughput (Average) in Mbps • Throughput (Max) in Mbps • Throughput (Min) in Mbps • Reliability
Expected Result	The network test expects to provide network KPIs measurements. These measurements include metrics related to the service that is provided to end users. Therefore, the expected results should validate the optimal performance of the network according to the network requirements that have been identified for each use case.	

Table 33: Network oriented TC addressing 5G slice performance

Testcase ID	Test_ID_02	
Trial site	<Trial site ID>	
Testcase type	5G Network Performance_Bandwidth_slice	
Description	<p>The purpose of this network slice test is to measure 5G network performance KPIs and validate its performance according to the use case requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Throughput (UL/DL) • E2E Latency • Packet Loss <p>The monitoring probes, as presented in the Test environment, are relevant at the 5GRAN Level, 5G Transport level, 5G CN, virtualized Infrastructure and External test application. The traffic generator/measurements are performed between UE <> NetApps</p>	
Test environment and deployment	<p style="text-align: center;">Testcase measurement architecture</p>	
Cross-referencing	Relevant NetApps	NetApp ID: 5G Network performance
	Reference Service	N/A
	Reference Experiment	N/A
5G Network Environment	5G Network settings / configuration	3GPP 5G SA Rel.16 SA 5G Slice: eMBB/URLLC 5G SA RAN details: SST 5G SA Core: 5G IP/Backhaul:
	Testcase traffic flows	<p>The testcase traffic flow are defined between different 5G testbed Traffic_Generator_Receiver points (TGR_1;) measured at different network Probe points (P_1; P_2; P_3; P_4), traffic generator and probes as testbed’s availability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DL traffic flow <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MIN/MAX • UL traffic flow <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MIN/MAX • E2E Latency measurements

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ RTT/ms • Packet loss <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ % packet loss • Jitter <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Deviation ms • User Experienced Downlink Data Rate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MIN/MAX • User Experienced Uplink Data Rate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MIN/MAX • Application Guaranteed Data Rate • Guaranteed Network Latency 																																				
	<p>Network performance & functional requirements and KPIs</p>	<p>The measured KPIs are compared against the D1.1 network KPIs</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="704 636 1367 1037"> <thead> <tr> <th>KPI</th> <th>Port of Antwerp</th> <th>Galati Port</th> <th>Athens logistics hub</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Latency (max)</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>DL Throughput (min)</td> <td>30</td> <td>20</td> <td>30</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UL Throughput (min)</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Packet Loss</td> <td>%</td> <td>%</td> <td>%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Jitter</td> <td>Ms</td> <td>Ms</td> <td>ms</td> </tr> <tr> <td>User Experienced UL</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>User Experienced DL</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Guaranteed Network Latency</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>KPIs measurements results analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation results 	KPI	Port of Antwerp	Galati Port	Athens logistics hub	Latency (max)	20	20	20	DL Throughput (min)	30	20	30	UL Throughput (min)	20	20	20	Packet Loss	%	%	%	Jitter	Ms	Ms	ms	User Experienced UL				User Experienced DL				Guaranteed Network Latency			
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<p>Components and Configuration</p>	<p>IoT/T&L components (e.g., sensors, IoT gateways, AGVs, etc)</p>	<p>N/A for network performance tests</p>																																				
	<p>Networking components (e.g., traffic generators, network emulators, network probes)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic generator using iperfv3 • ICMP tool • Network probes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Testbed specific tool • Monitoring software tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Testbed specific tool 																																				
	<p>Components of the SUT</p>	<p>N/A</p>																																				
	<p>Application-level Configuration</p>	<p>N/A</p>																																				
<p>Key Use-case requirements and KPIs</p>	<p>Functional requirements</p>	<p>N/A</p>																																				
	<p>Service KPIs</p>																																					

		N/A (only network KPIs will be measured)
	Secondary Service KPIs	N/A
Test procedure	Test location / route	The test is performed at the different network entry points; see Probes_Traffic_Generator test case diagram.
	Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5G network integration completed • Probes/Generators installed • Monitoring software tools installed.
	Testcase steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic is generated through the network (use of ICMP/ping and iPerf) • Generators/Probes/Monitoring tool send/receive traffic and perform measurements • KPIs tables are completed (CSV format) • KPIs are evaluated • Final results analysis
Measurements	Methodology	<p>E2E latency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Network basic KPIs description <p>Throughput</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Network basic KPIs description <p>Packet Loss</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Network basic KPIs description <p>Jitter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Network basic KPIs description
	Measurement Points	Network traffic generators, probes and software collection tools are used in the 5G testbeds in different points, see figure.
	Calculation process	<p>Values to be measured and computed (CSV format):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latency (Average) in ms • Latency (Max) in ms • Latency (Min) in ms • Throughput (Average) in Mbps • Throughput (Max) in Mbps • Throughput (Min) in Mbps
Expected Result	The network test expects to provide network KPIs measurements. These measurements include metrics related to the service that is provided to end users. Therefore, the expected results should validate the optimal performance of the network according to the network requirements that have been identified for each use case.	

Table 34: Network oriented TC addressing Manual slice instantiation and termination

Testcase ID	Test_ID_03	
Trial site	Galati trial site	
Testcase type	5G_Test_Bed_Manual slice instantiation and termination	
Description	The test case presents the slice creation (manually on the RAN & Core equipment) and dynamically for the NetApps, run connectivity test towards a test IP over the newly created slice and manual termination of the slice	
Test environment and deployment	<p style="text-align: center;">Testcase measurement architecture</p>	
Cross-referencing	Relevant NetApps	N/A (These values are just for testcases related to NetApps or vertical services.)
	Reference Service	N/A
	Reference Experiment	N/A
5G Network Environment	5G Network settings / configuration	<p>3GPP 5G SA Rel.16 SA</p> <p>5G SA RAN details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ RAN slice template: SST1/SST2 ○ gNB configuration: manual <p>5G SA Core:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core elements • Slice templates: SST1 • Slice configuration: manual • DNN for configured slices (1/2): SNSSAI • 5G QoS: throughput, latency <p>5G Backhaul:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gNB N2/N3 integration: high speed 10Gbps • Transport network configuration: manual/dynamic • Transport QoS: latency <p>5G Slices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slice_1; SST1 • Slice_2; SST2 <p>Facility Architecture for KPIs/performance:</p> <p>5G Virtualization for NetApps:</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Configuration: Dynamic • Deployment time
	<p>Testcase traffic flows</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic flow 1 from TG_1 to NetApps VM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ UL MIN/MAX ○ DL MIN/MAX ○ Latency
	<p>Network performance & functional requirements and KPIs</p>	<p>Based on D1.1 the slicing capability must exist and the service creation time should be less than 90 minutes.</p> <p>KPIs measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service creation time (min)
<p>Components and Configuration</p>	<p>IoT/T&L components (e.g., sensors, IoT gateways, AGVs, etc)</p>	<p>N/A</p>
	<p>Networking components (e.g., traffic generators, network emulators)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5G enabled terminal (smartphone) • 5G RAN & core network
	<p>Components of the SUT</p>	<p>N/A</p>
	<p>Application-level Configuration</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Key Use-case requirements and KPIs</p>	<p>Functional requirements</p>	<p>Not relevant</p>
	<p>Service KPIs</p>	<p>N/A (network KPIs will be measured)</p>
	<p>Secondary Service KPIs</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Test procedure</p>	<p>Test location / route</p>	<p>5G RAN & Core</p>

	Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5G network (RAN & Core) integration Virtualized Infra and Orchestration
	Testcase steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> include slice creation steps (manual) Measure the time for slice creation, starting from the actual time of issuing commands in RAN & core side until the moment the slice is actually provisioned and becomes available for use test traffic on the newly created slice delete the slice
Measurements	Methodology	Configuration steps info
	Measurement Points	E2E service time creation
	Calculation process	Measurements of the slice creation
Expected Result	Successful creation of a slice in the 5G network in less than 90 minutes, test the service performance. Delete manually the slice (check in configuration the deletion and test that no connectivity is allowed anymore)	

Table 35: Network oriented TC addressing 5G slice QoS evaluation

Testcase ID	Test_ID_04
Trial site	<Trial site ID>
Testcase type	5G Network Load Performance QoS for slice
Description	<p>The purpose of this network test is to measure 5G network performance KPIs in the 5G network load stress, for the main 5G network service KPIs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Throughput (UL/DL) E2E Network Latency Packet Loss <p>The monitoring probes, as presented in the Test environment, are relevant at the 5GRAN Level, 5G Transport level, 5G CN, virtualized Infrastructure and External test application. Series of traffic generators/traffic collectors are implemented/deployed in the testbed, empowering the traffic generation and traffic collection and measurements in different 5G Network points.</p>
Test environment and deployment	<p>The diagram illustrates the test environment architecture. It shows a 5G UE (with a '5G UE test' box) connected to a 5G RAN. The RAN connects to a Transport Network, which then connects to 5G SA CN and DC IP. The DC IP connects to a Virtualized Infrastructure block containing NetApps VMs and Test Servers. The Virtualized Infrastructure is connected to External Test Servers. Traffic flows are indicated by arrows, and various probes (Probe 1-4) and traffic generators/receivers are positioned at different network points.</p>

		Testcase measurement architecture																								
Cross-referencing	Relevant NetApps	N/A	5G QoS Network performance																							
	Reference Service	N/A																								
	Reference Experiment	N/A																								
5G Network Environment	5G Network settings / configuration	3GPP 5G SA Rel.16 SA 5G SA RAN details: 5G SA Core: 5G IP/Backhaul:																								
	Testcase traffic flows	<p>The testcase traffic flow are defined between different 5G testbed Traffic_Generator_Receiver points. The network is load at the RAN, Transport, Core, DC IP and Virtualized Infrastructure level, as presented in the measurement architecture:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5G_UE_test to a test server (TG_1 – TG_3), UPF level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ UL/DL load tests traffic • Transport Network load (TG_2 – TG_3) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ UL/DL load tests traffic <p>5G_UE service slice tests for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DL traffic flow <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MIN/MAX • UL traffic flow <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MIN/MAX • Latency measurements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ RTT/ms • Packet loss <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ % packet loss • Jitter <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Deviation ms • Packet Delivery Ratio • Coverage area • 5G System Bandwidth • Slice Reliability 																								
	Network performance & functional requirements and KPIs	<p>The measured KPIs are compared against the D1.1 network KPIs</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="703 1581 1365 1850"> <thead> <tr> <th>KPI</th> <th>Port of Antwerp</th> <th>Galati Port</th> <th>Athens logistics hub</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Latency (max)</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>DL Throughput (min)</td> <td>30</td> <td>20</td> <td>30</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UL Throughput (min)</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Packet Loss</td> <td>%</td> <td>%</td> <td>%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Jitter</td> <td>ms</td> <td>ms</td> <td>ms</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>KPIs measurements results analysis:</p>		KPI	Port of Antwerp	Galati Port	Athens logistics hub	Latency (max)	20	20	20	DL Throughput (min)	30	20	30	UL Throughput (min)	20	20	20	Packet Loss	%	%	%	Jitter	ms	ms
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UL Throughput (min)	20	20	20																							
Packet Loss	%	%	%																							
Jitter	ms	ms	ms																							

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluation results
Components and Configuration	IoT/T&L components (e.g., sensors, IoT gateways, AGVs, etc)	N/A for network performance tests
	Networking components (e.g., traffic generators, network emulators, network probes)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traffic generator using iperfv3 ICMP tool Network probes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Testbed specific tool Monitoring software tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Testbed specific tool
	Components of the SUT	N/A
	Application-level Configuration	N/A
Key Use-case requirements and KPIs	Functional requirements	N/A
	Service KPIs	N/A (only network KPIs will be measured)
	Secondary Service KPIs	N/A
Test procedure	Test location / route	The test is performed at the different network entry points; see Probes_Traffic_Generator test case diagram.
	Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5G network integration completed Probes/Generators installed Monitoring software tools installed.
	Testcase steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traffic is generated through the network (use of ICMP/ping and iPerf) Generators/Probes/Monitoring tool send/receive traffic and perform measurements KPIs tables are completed (CSV format) KPIs are evaluated Final results analysis
Measurements	Methodology	E2E latency <ul style="list-style-type: none"> See Network basic KPIs description Throughput <ul style="list-style-type: none"> See Network basic KPIs description Packet Loss <ul style="list-style-type: none"> See Network basic KPIs description

		<p>Jitter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Network basic KPIs description <p>Reliability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Network basic KPIs description
	<p>Measurement Points</p>	<p>Network traffic generators, probes and software collection tools are used in the 5G testbeds in different points, see figure.</p>
	<p>Calculation process</p>	<p>Values to be measured and computed (CSV format):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latency (Average) in ms • Latency (Max) in ms • Latency (Min) in ms • Throughput (Average) in Mbps • Throughput (Max) in Mbps • Throughput (Min) in Mbps • Reliability
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>The network test expects to provide network KPIs measurements. These measurements include metrics related to the service that is provided to end users. Therefore, the expected results should validate the optimal performance of the network according to the network requirements that have been identified for each use case.</p>	